

Policy Cloud
Cloud for Data-Driven Policy Management

CLOUD FOR DATA-DRIVEN POLICY MANAGEMENT

Project Number: 870675

Start Date of Project: 01/01/2020

Duration: 36 months

D4.3 Reusable Model & Analytical Tools: Design and Open Specification 2

Dissemination Level	PU
Due Date of Deliverable	31/08/2021, M20
Actual Submission Date	31/08/2021
Work Package	WP4 Reusable Models & Analytical Tools
Task	WP4
Type	Report
Approval Status	
Version	1.0
Number of Pages	p.1 – p.76

Abstract: Second version of the Internal architecture of the Integrated Acquisition and Analytics Layer, responsible for the a) integration of analytical tools in extensible manner, b) registration of new data sources c) applying the required transformation and cleaning on the data fusion pass, d) specification and design of the built-in analytics tools for Situational Knowledge, e) Opinion Mining & Sentiment Analysis, f) Social Dynamics & Behavioral Data analysis, and g) (new) Optimization & Reusability of Analytical Tool section.

The information in this document reflects only the author's views and the European Community is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The information in this document is provided "as is" without guarantee or warranty of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to the fitness of the information for a particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at his/ her sole risk and liability. This deliverable is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

PolicyCLOUD has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 870675.

Versioning and Contribution History

Version	Date	Reason	Author
0.1	16/06/2021	Initial version	Yosef Moatti (IBM)
0.2	30/06/2021	ATOS content	María Ángeles Sanguino, Tomás Pariente (ATOS)
0.3	01/07/2021	Addition of the draft for seamless (4.4)	Yosef Moatti
0.4	05/07/2021	Enhancement of seamless (4.4) Address Yosef's comments in section 5	Pavlos Kranas
0.5	05/07/2021	New version of 4,3 - Social Dynamics	Nikitas Sgouros
0.6	06/07/2021	Formatting of 4.3	Yosef Moatti
0.7	06/07/2021	Extensive reformatting of all the document	Yosef Moatti
0.8	07/07/2021	Further reformatting	Yosef Moatti
0.9	08/07/2021	Change in 4.3 introduction	Nikitas Sgouros
0.10	12/07/2021	Cloud Gateways, Data Cleaning Enhanced Interoperability	Argyro Mavrogiorgou, George Manias, Thanos Kiourtis
0.11	14/07/2021	Update of T4.1 API	Yosef Moatti
0.12	19/07/2021	Section 2.3 "security and legal concerns" added	IBM
0.13	20/07/2021	Same as 0.12 but with all changes accepted	
0.14	22/07/2021	Reformatting of the full document	Yosef Moatti
0.15	23/07/2021	Integration of ethical, legal, regulatory, and societal requirements Enhanced Executive Summary / Conclusion + many small fixes	Martim Taborda Barata & Andrea Strippoli (ICTLC) Yosef Moatti
0.16	25/07/2021	DAA updates, infrastructure, api and components	Oshrit Feder
0.17	25/07/2021	Full review of the document	Yosef Moatti
0.18	26/07/2021	Additional review and fixes from tasks leaders	Yosef Moatti
0.19	27/07/2021	Changes in section 2	Oshrit Feder
0.20	27/07/2021	Fixes for 4.1 and 4.2	Maria Sangino
0.21	27/07/2021	Version sent for internal review. This is a full draft except for 4.1 and 4.2 which should be fixed by ATOS authors	Yosef Moatti
0.22	29/07/2021	Partial fixes following Pavlos Kranas' review	Yosef Moatti

0.23	01/08/2021	Partial fixes following Rafael del Hoyo's review	Yosef Moatti
0.24	19/08/2021	Version ready for second round of internal review	All authors
0.25	19/08/2021	Same as 0.24 but with all changes accepted	
0.26	24/08/2021	Handling of Pavlos' second internal review	Yosef Moatti
0.27	25/08/2021	Changes in 4.2.3 to further address one of the interim review comments	Maria Sangino
0.28	27/08/2021	Second internal review of Rafael	Rafael de Hoyo
0.29	29/08/2021	Handling of Rafael's comments	Yosef Moatti
0.30	30/08/2021	Quality check	Argyro Mavrogiorgou
1.0	30/08/2021	Handle Argyro's comments Submitted version	Yosef Moatti

Author List

Organisation	Name
IBM	Ofer Biran, Oshrit Feder, Yosef Moatti
LXS	Pavlos Kranas, Javier Pereira, Alejandro Ramiro
ATOS	María Ángeles Sanguino, Tomás Pariente
UPRC	Argyro Mavrogiorgou, Thanos Kiourtis, George Manias, Nikitas Sgouros, Konstantinos Koutsoukos
OKS	Kostas Nasias
ICTLC	Martim Taborda Barata, Andrea Strippoli

Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
AO	Analytic Owner
EC	European Commission
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GTD	Global Terrorism Database
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
ID	Identification (number/code)
ML	Machine Learning
NFS	Network File System
NER	Named Entity Recognition
NLP	Natural Language Processing
PDT	Policy Development Toolkit
PM	Policy Maker
POS	Part-of-Speech
REST	Representational State Transfer
SAF	Seamless Analytical Framework
SKA	Situational Knowledge Acquisition

Contents

Versioning and Contribution History.....	2
Author List.....	3
Abbreviations and Acronyms.....	4
Contents.....	5
List of Figures.....	7
Executive Summary.....	8
1 Introduction.....	9
1.1 Positioning of this deliverable.....	9
1.2 WP4 Objectives.....	9
1.3 WP4 Positioning and Relations to other Work Packages.....	9
2 Data Acquisition and Analytics Layer.....	11
2.1 General Architecture and Roles.....	11
2.1.1 Updates since D4.1.....	11
2.1.2 Architecture and analytic functions APIs.....	11
2.2 Extensibility and Reusability.....	16
2.2.1 Updates since D4.1.....	16
2.2.2 Data Source Registration.....	16
2.2.3 Analytic Function Registration.....	16
2.2.4 Analytics Function Invocation.....	17
2.3 Security and Legal concerns.....	18
2.3.1 Updates since D4.1.....	18
2.3.2 Logging Service.....	18
2.3.3 Ethical, legal, regulatory, and societal considerations.....	19
3 Data Fusion with Processing and Initial Analytics.....	22
3.1 Cloud Gateways (Task T3.3).....	23
3.1.1 Updates since D4.1.....	23
3.2 Enhanced Interoperability & Data Cleaning (Task T4.2).....	24
3.2.1 Updates since D4.1.....	24
3.2.2 Data Cleaning.....	25
3.2.3 Enhanced Interoperability.....	28

4	Analytic on Data at Rest	35
4.1	Situational Knowledge Acquisition & Analysis (Task T4.3)	36
4.1.1	Updates since D4.1	36
4.1.2	Y2 functionality extracted from pilots	36
4.1.3	SKA components	37
4.2	Opinion Mining & Sentiment Analysis (Task T4.4)	40
4.2.1	Updates since D4.1	40
4.2.2	Y2 functionality extracted from pilots	40
4.2.3	Sentiment Analysis component	41
4.3	Social Dynamics & Behavioral Data Analytics (Task T4.5)	43
4.3.1	Updates since D4.1	43
4.3.2	Introduction.....	43
4.3.3	Simulation Environment for Social Dynamics.....	44
4.3.4	Meta-simulation Environment for Policy Analysis and Design.....	54
4.3.5	Future steps.....	58
4.3.6	Conclusion	59
4.4	Optimization & Reusability of Analytical Tools (Task T4.6)	62
4.4.1	Updates since D4.1	62
4.4.2	User Story and Motivation.....	62
4.4.3	Architecture	63
4.4.4	Seamless within Policy Cloud	63
5	Cloud Platform and Software Tools.....	67
5.1	Updates since D4.1	67
5.2	Kubernetes cluster	67
5.3	OpenWhisk cluster.....	68
5.4	LeanXcale database.....	68
5.5	Spark cluster	71
5.6	Object storage	71
6	Conclusion.....	73
7	References.....	74

List of Figures

Figure 1 - WP4 interface with WP3 and WP5.....	10
Figure 2 - Data acquisition and Analytic layer	12
Figure 3 - Data Sourced Path.....	15
Figure 4 - Example of a function registration	17
Figure 5 - the streaming data path	22
Figure 6 - Data Cleaning workflow	25
Figure 7 - Data Processing Layer	32
Figure 8 - Ontology Mapping Step.....	33
Figure 9 - Seamless analytics on ingested data.....	35
Figure 10 - Example workflow for Opinion mining Component using apache nifi.....	39
Figure 11 - Overall architecture of the Politika simulation environment	45
Figure 12 - I/O specification of the Social Dynamics simulator.....	46
Figure 13 - Concurrent execution scheme of the Social Dynamics Simulator.....	53
Figure 14 - Screenshot of simple Simulation Model in Politika with Radicalization	55
Figure 15 - Example policy structure used by the meta-simulation environment	56
Figure 16 - Politika Processing Pipeline.....	57
Figure 17 - Screenshot of the Politika GUI for managing network data and visualizing the execution of simulations on the population network	61
Figure 18 - Visualization example of scaled attribute values for each individual in a population.....	62
Figure 19 - Visualization example of a connectivity matrix	62
Figure 20 - Seamless high level architecture	63
Figure 21 - Seamless Analytical Framework with Data Mover	64
Figure 22 - LeanXcale datastore architectural design.....	69

Executive Summary

This document is the second architecture deliverable for WP4. It is an incremental update of PolicyCLOUD deliverable D4.1, and as such it repeats some of the content and adds new developments and work to do.

It provides an update of the architecture of the Data Acquisition and Analytics Layer. As such, it details the included data analytic and transformation tools, the cloud platform and software tools that are planned at this point to be used for the implementation of the PolicyCLOUD platform towards the demonstration in D4.4 Reusable Model & Analytical Tools: Software Prototype 2.

In essence, the Data Acquisition and Analytics Layer provides an extensible framework for data source and analytic tools, controlling the full data pass from the data sources through filtering, transformation and initial analytic, to hot storage and then to cold storage while enabling deeper analytics by the registered analytic tools on the ingested data at any time.

We added for each sub-section (or when relevant for each section) an “Update since D4.1” sub-section which summarized the evolution from D4.1. In the following paragraph we give a summary of all the reported changes from D4.1.

- In Section 2, we updated the registration APIs for the sake of legal concerns. These changes are revisited and further commented in the new section 2.3: “Security and Legal concerns”.
- In section 3, the main novelty for Enhanced Interoperability is the SemAI hybrid mechanism and its associated changes. Concerning the Cleaning technology, we report of additional rules which render this cleaning technology more general.
- In section 4 we present in D4.3 a major update of the “Social Dynamics and Behavioral Data Analytics” technology (4.3). In addition we added 4.4: “Optimization & Reusability of Analytical Tools” covering task T4.6.
- In section 5 which covers the cloud platform and the software tools for PolicyCLOUD we have no notable change which proves the soundness of our initial choices as reported in D4.1.

1 Introduction

1.1 Positioning of this deliverable

This document is the second architecture deliverable for WP4. It is an incremental update of the PolicyCLOUD deliverable D4.1. As such, it repeats some of the content and adds new development, work to do, and sometime descriptions of new technologies (e.g., 4.4). Each of the topics presented in this document is preceded by a short summary of the updates since D4.1.

1.2 WP4 Objectives

The major objectives of WP4 as stated in the PolicyCLOUD project proposal and Grant agreement were to:

- Provide the framework for data fusion and aggregation – for different data sources types
- Provide data cleaning ensuring quality of information, sources reliability assessment, reliability-based selection of information sources
- Provide sentiment analysis techniques for policy assessment
- Analyze the social and behavioral data and requirements provided by social science experts for data selection in a given case
- Decouple the analytical models and tools from the underlying infrastructure and datastores, assuring their reusability.

To fulfill these objectives, WP4 provides an extensible framework for applying various analytics on different data sources, through the development of the Data Acquisition and Analytics Layer and the basic analytic tools that have been registered in it.

In this second version of the report (D4.3), we provide an additional section, the “Optimization and Reusability of Analytical tools” (4.4) that was missing in the first version (D4.1) and we also reported the evolution, sometime significant, of the other already introduced technologies.

1.3 WP4 Positioning and Relations to other Work Packages

WP4 is responsible for the Data Acquisition and Analytics Layer, which is the central layer of PolicyCLOUD, between the cloud infrastructure and Policy layers. This layer provides on one hand, the functionality for data ingestion from various sources while applying filtering and initial analytics, preparing it for deeper analytics on longer term storage (DB, object storage), and on the other hand, various analytical tools that can be used by the upper layers of the PolicyCLOUD platform.

From the aspect of Work Packages partitioning, the Data Acquisition and Analytics Layer is under the responsibility of WP4 (Reusable Models & Analytical Tools) and its tasks, with a strong relation to Task 3.3 (Cloud Gateways) and Task 3.6 (Data Governance Model, Protection and Privacy Enforcement) of WP3. In

Figure 1 we show the conceptual model from the work packages partitioning point of view and the WP4 interfaces to WP3 below and WP5 above, as provided in the Grant Agreement document.

FIGURE 1 - WP4 INTERFACE WITH WP3 AND WP5

2 Data Acquisition and Analytics Layer

2.1 General Architecture and Roles

2.1.1 Updates since D4.1

From D4.1 two Use Cases were demonstrated end-to-end during the interim review. Furthermore, after this review, we had discussions concerning the other use cases and till now, we did not detect changes needed to accommodate these additional use cases. All this proves that both the general architecture and the design of the APIs were both sound and general. Still one change should be noted which is the addition of new fields in the registration APIs. These changes were nonfunctional since their goal is to answer legal concerns that were raised and discussed this past year.

2.1.2 Architecture and analytic functions APIs

The Data Acquisition and Analytics layer (DAA) is responsible for the orchestration and integration of all the components of the DAA layer (analytic functions, data sources, data repository) as well as providing the external interface for the layer's exploiters – analytic owners, data source owners, and the Policy layer (through which the end user applies desired analytics). Its roles include forming the proper setup of the registered analytic functions and data sources to ensure the correct data ingest process (applying the required ingest-time analytics/transformation – in both Ingest-now and Streaming modes), (see definitions page 14) and applying the requested analytics on the requested data source. The DAA API Gateway is implemented as a set of serverless functions (in the OpenWhisk cluster), where the state is managed both on the OpenWhisk itself (e.g., analytic functions' metadata) and the database.

There are two types of functions:

1. Analytics Ingest / Transformation Functions, are used to apply initial analytics and/or transformation on the data fusion path of data sources before stored in PolicyCLOUD backend.
2. Analytics Functions, which will be activated by PolicyCLOUD users through the Policy Layer, to perform an analysis on a specified data source (which has already been ingested / transformed) to provide analytics insights that can be further used in policy decisions.

FIGURE 2 - DATA ACQUISITION AND ANALYTIC LAYER

According to the numbers in Figure 2:

1. Analytic Owners are responsible for the functionality of the Ingest Functions which they register on the PolicyCLOUD platform (and, specifically, using the Data Acquisition and Analytics layer API). On Ingest Function registration the following parameters should be provided:
 - a. name: function name
 - b. kind: relates to the function implementation type (e.g., java8, image based, etc.)
 - c. filename: jar filename containing the function code
 - d. main: specify the function main class
 - e. image: image name residing in the container registry service if kind is image (optional)
 - f. function parameters: function parameters (Json)
 - g. type: analytic / analytic-ingest
 - h. category: Data-Cleaning / Data-Interoperability / Situational-Knowledge / Opinion-Mining / Social-Dynamic
 - i. description: function description and usage
 - j. Expected input data schema/format
 - k. purpose: for data access enforcement
 - l. biasDoc – this parameter permits, and in fact could even oblige (e.g., by checking that this parameter has a minimal required length and/or that an attachment of a defined format and filesize range is included), the Analytic Owners to input bias management documentation, providing information on the specific measures taken to address the risk of biases inherent to the functioning of the Analytics Ingest Function. It could also permit / oblige Analytic Owners to upload or indicate one or more unit test datasets on which the Analytics Ingest Function can be applied, so as to demonstrate that resulting bias

- measurements do not exceed a given maximum (in other words, that the specific measures taken to address the risk of biases are functioning effectively, as intended);
- m. **tradeoffsDoc** - this parameter permits, and in fact could even oblige (e.g., by checking that this parameter has a minimal required length and/or that an attachment of a defined format and filesize range is included), the Analytic Owners to input documentation on the management of trade-offs, providing information on the relevant trade-offs encountered, decisions made concerning the balancing of competing requirements (e.g., result precision versus fairness) and measures taken to implement and document those decisions.

PolicyCLOUD administration privileges are required for registration of Analytics Ingest Functions. Internally, Analytics Ingest Functions will be deployed as OpenWhisk¹ functions. At a later phase of the Project, a registration tool will be developed to make this registration process simpler, as well as to enforce a scheme of common parameters. Enhanced Interoperability & Data Cleaning (T4.2) will be a built-in Analytics Ingest Function in PolicyCLOUD.

Each ingest function is expected to read the incoming data from the request's message parameter (JSON string), and to return the transformed message as a JSON string as well. The result JSON string might be the input of the next ingest function, or the transformation result written to PolicyCLOUD's backend.

2. Similar responsibilities apply to Analytic Owners regarding the registration of Analytics Functions (see API parameters above (1)).
3. Data Owners are responsible for the registration of Data Sources into the PolicyCLOUD platform. Upon a datasource registration, the relevant data is imported to PolicyCLOUD backend after being transformed by applying a group of pipelined ingest functions on it (e.g., filtering/cleaning), keeping in the PolicyCLOUD data store only extracted knowledge, as opposed to the whole raw data. There are three different types of datasource registration:
 - a. **Streaming** –data will be continuously streamed from one or more external sources (e.g. twitter) into the PolicyCLOUD data store.
 - b. **Ingest-now** –external (or local) data which should be ingested into the PolicyCLOUD data store.
 - c. **External** – an external data source that can be queried / analysed upon demand, without ingesting data outside of such queries / analyses.

During the datasource registration, the CloudGateway (T3.3) component is invoked to retrieve the data source content.

¹ <https://openwhisk.apache.org/>

On Data Source registration, the following parameters should be provided:

- a. Name
 - b. Type (Streaming / Ingest-now / External)
 - c. Description
 - d. Source specification (streaming details, source data location, source URL, access method, credentials etc.)
 - e. Schema / metadata
 - f. Permissions – by whom (public / specified user list) and for what purpose the data can be used for (Analytics Functions which are to be applied to a Data Source should have been registered for purposes which are identical or compatible with the purposes identified for that Data Source)
 - g. Analytics Ingest Function + parameters if applicable
 - h. biasDoc – this parameter permits, and in fact could even oblige (e.g., by checking that this parameter has a minimal required length and/or that an attachment of a defined format and filesize range is included), the Data Owner to input bias management documentation, providing information on the bias detection methods applied to the Data Source, the specific biases identified and the specific measures taken to address any such biases.
 - i. GDPRDoc – this parameter permits, and in fact could even oblige (e.g., by checking that this parameter has a minimal required length and/or that an attachment of a defined format and filesize range is included), the Data Owners to input privacy / data protection management documentation which, in particular, should indicate whether any personal data is included within the Data Source and, if so, the measures taken to ensure that the Data Source can be ingested onto the platform in compliance with the applicable data protection and regulatory framework related to the processing of personal data, as defined by the GDPR and other applicable data protection laws (e.g., to ensure compliance with the principles of lawfulness, transparency and purpose limitation under the GDPR, considering the purposes for which the personal data within the Data Source were originally collected and the purposes for which those personal data will be further processed via the platform).
 - j. authDoc – this parameter, permits, and in fact could even oblige (e.g., by checking that this parameter has a minimal required length and/or that an attachment of a defined format and filesize range is included), the Data Owners to input documentation to demonstrate that the registration of the Data Source has been authorised by relevant rightsholders (or that such authorisation is not required under applicable laws).
4. The data of a registered Data Source will be ingested into PolicyCLOUD according to the Data Source type: as can be seen in Figure 2, for Streaming Data Sources, the registered Analytics Ingest Function(s) will be triggered whenever new data is available; for Ingest-now Data Sources, data will be ingested upon registration and processed by the registered Analytics Ingest Function(s); and for External Data Sources, data will be read (and possibly processed by registered Analytics Ingest Function(s)) at the direct request of users for analytics.

FIGURE 3 - DATA SOURCED PATH

5. PolicyCLOUD users can list, through the platform’s dashboard, registered Data Sources and Analytics Functions together with their metadata, description and required parameters. PolicyCLOUD users can apply a registered Analytics Function on a given Data Source. Validation for this application will be performed according to the user’s credentials, the permissions registered for the Data Source, and the defined purpose(s) registered for the Analytics Function (as noted, Analytics Functions which are to be applied to a Data Source should have been registered for purposes which are identical or compatible with the purposes identified for that Data Source).
6. The Policy Layer will interact with the Data Acquisition and Analytics layer to retrieve the registered Data Sources and Analytic Functions, and to apply the selected Analytics Function on the selected Data Source while enforcing permissions.

On applying analytic function on datasource, the following parameters should be provided:

- UserCredentials: (TBD by the enforcement point)
- Function: Analytic function name
- Data-source: data source name

2.2 Extensibility and Reusability

2.2.1 Updates since D4.1

Please refer to 2.1.1 which also mostly apply to this subsection.

2.2.2 Data Source Registration

PolicyCLOUD administration privilege is required for a data source registration. Internally, the data source details will be saved in the PolicyCLOUD store, CloudGateway would be called to pull the datasource data, kafka topics will be created for buffering and interaction with the CloudGateway, OpenWhisk rule and trigger will be deployed for activation of the specified Analytic-ingest functions whenever data is available (e.g., on a Kafka topic used as a connector) and according to the data source type also the following:

- a. **Streaming, Ingest-now** – At the time of the user request all the data was already ingested to the PolicyCLOUD store. Over time, the data might reside partially in the LeanXscale database and partially in the object storage, but this will be transparent to the Analytic Function (with the seamless component).
- b. **External** – an Analytic-ingest function can be specified also for External type, in this case whenever a read is performed from the external source (driven by a PolicyCLOUD user requests for applying analytic), the data will be processed by the Analytic-ingest function before being passed to the regular Analytic function. Additional data pre-processing is being pushed down to the external datastore provider and the PolicyCLOUD platform only retrieve the result of this pre-processing, thus never having complete access to the data set itself.

The Data Acquisition and Analytics layer provides an API to list all the registered Data Sources with their registration parameters, to be exploited by the Policy Layer.

2.2.3 Analytic Function Registration

PolicyCLOUD administration privileges are required for the registration of Analytics Ingest Function(s) or Analytics Function(s). Internally, these functions will be deployed as OpenWhisk functions. At a later phase of the Project, a registration tool will be developed to make their registration process simpler, as well as to enforce a scheme of common parameters. Enhanced Interoperability & Data Cleaning (Task T4.2) will be a built-in Analytics Ingest Function in PolicyCLOUD, and Situational Knowledge Acquisition & Analytics (Task T4.3), Opinion Mining & Sentiment Analysis (T4.4.) are built-in Analytics Functions in PolicyCLOUD. Concerning Social Dynamics & Behavioral Data Analytics (Task T4.5), we are currently in the process of integrating this technology within the PolicyCLOUD framework.

Analytic functions are developed by Analytic owners and can be implemented either in python or in java or node.js, and should follow Openwhisk action implementation guidelines.

DAA includes a common gitlab structure for functions' code registry and common container registry for functions' docker images with all required dependencies.

Files and images are automatically pulled from PolicyCLOUD gitlab service during function registration to create the serverless function.

The registration scheme of an Analytics Function includes list of parameters that must be specified. More details can be found at the D5.2 deliverable. - In Figure 4, we can see an example of the attached registration information:

```
{
  "configuration": null,
  "dateCreated": "2020-06-23, Thu, 00:00:00 CEST",
  "description": "The implementation of the exploratory data at-rest analysis for a specific dataset",
  "outputGraph": "heat map",
  "endpoint": "http://www.example.com/analytical-tool/aggregationDataAnalysis",
  "uuid": "a3d06b6c-c253-4cf0-8455-91ldb425446",
  "serviceType": {
    "dateCreated": "2020-06-23, Thu, 00:00:00 CEST",
    "segmentTypes": [],
    "description": "Provided by ATOS",
    "name": "Exploratory Dataset Analysis Tool",
    "id": 3
  },
  "name": "Exploratory Dataset Analysis Tool",
  "id": 3,
  "parameters": [
    {
      "valueConstraints": [
        {
          "value": [],
          "constraintType": "DEFAULT"
        }
      ],
      "unit": null,
      "valueType": "ENUM",
      "name": "fields",
      "description": "field to be used for the aggregation",
      "id": "1888df82-843a-406a-b78c-elcddb68cc41",
      "evaluationTypesAllowed": [
        "RANGE"
      ]
    }
  ],
}
```

FIGURE 4 - EXAMPLE OF A FUNCTION REGISTRATION

2.2.4 Analytics Function Invocation

The Data Acquisition and Analytics layer provides an API to list all the registered Analytics Functions with their registration parameters, allowing to invoke a selected Function on a selected Data Source. A common scheme will be provided for Analytics Function invocation.

2.3 Security and Legal concerns

2.3.1 Updates since D4.1

This section was added in D4.3

2.3.2 Logging Service

As noted in D3.3 [37], it is essential for the PolicyCLOUD platform to incorporate adequate technical and organisational security measures, developed as a result of a dedicated security risk assessment targeting potential threats. To this extent, a secure logging service is critical for security. Among other usages, logging permits to identify security threats, to analyse suspected incidents (forensic analysis), to monitor policy violations and to provide information for unusual conditions. Furthermore, logging is also critical for debugging both performance and functional problems.

Logging further serves to ensure appropriate auditability of the AI-based functions (such as Analytics Ingest Functions and Analytics Functions) which are executed on the PolicyCLOUD platform – in other words, “the ability of an AI system to undergo the assessment of the system’s algorithms, data and design processes” [38]. This serves to identify further legal, regulatory, ethical and societal requirements identified in D3.3 [37], notably, “Mechanisms facilitating the auditability of AI systems (e.g., traceability of the development process, the sourcing of training data, and the logging of the AI system processes, outcomes, and positive and negative impacts) should be put in place”.

During this phase of the project, we have now implemented a standard logging service by deploying logstash², arguably the most popular open-source log management tool, on PolicyCLOUD’s Kubernetes infrastructure. The logging service is accessible to all PolicyCLOUD WPs using an HTTP API, and forms a centralized, project-wide infrastructure component. Each logging event is stored in a persistent file system enabled by NFS and ensures resiliency to pod failures and restarts.

For each PolicyCLOUD logging event, this service creates an additional entry in the log file(s). The list of fields that can be logged contain common basic fields, and additional fields which may be modified to fit the message created, so each message type might contain additional different fields. Common basic fields contain: wp, function, type, name, user, message, level.

As part of the Project’s efforts to harmonize the approach to data security around relevant standards, this system may be further assessed where needed to ensure that it is aligned (to the extent feasible)

² open server-side data processing pipeline <https://www.elastic.co/logstash/>

with the applicable requirements defined in ENISA’s (draft) “EUCS – Cloud Services Scheme” [40] – in particular, **OPS-10 to 16**.

2.3.3 Ethical, legal, regulatory, and societal considerations

As noted in D3.3 [37], the principle of data minimization, under Art. 5(1)(c) GDPR, requires the processing of personal data to be avoided altogether whenever feasible (favoring the use of aggregated or fully anonymised data if this does not substantially compromise the goals for which the processing of personal data was intended), or otherwise that such personal data be minimized – through, e.g., pseudo-anonymization and/or limitations on the amount of personal data collected and used.

Whenever personal data are included within a registered Data Source for further processing on the PolicyCLOUD platform, measures should be taken to ensure that those personal data were collected lawfully (under the principle of lawfulness – Art. 5(1)(a) GDPR), are processed for purposes which are compatible with those for which the data were originally collected (under the principle of purpose limitation – Art. 5(1)(b) GDPR), and that such data are as accurate and complete as possible (under the principle of accuracy – Art. 5(1)(e) GDPR), among other compliance requirements triggered under the GDPR and other applicable data protection laws.

In addition, applicable legal requirements may restrict the possibility to lawfully leverage a Data Source which might otherwise be considered appropriate from a practical perspective (i.e., useful towards the goal which a given PolicyCLOUD user might wish to achieve). Therefore, it is important to implement measures to assess whether each of the Data Sources envisaged to be used is subject to restrictions in terms of contractual limitations, database copyright protection, database sui generis right protection, and copyright protection.

Accuracy requirements, from the legal/regulatory and ethical/societal perspective, also apply to output which may be generated from data (whether personal or not). Measures should be taken to ensure that registered Analytics Ingest Functions and Analytics Functions do not handle data retrieved from registered Data Sources in such a manner that the outputs they generate misrepresents the information contained within such Data Sources. This speaks to the risk of bias inherent to such Functions, but also to the Data Sources themselves. Inaccurate or incomplete data/results may ultimately affect the output produced by the platform, causing misleading or erroneous conclusions, which may be relied on by PolicyCLOUD users to create policies. This, in turn, may lead to unforeseen and unjustified harmful impact on individuals and communities.

Any operations performed by such Functions on data should be methodically logged to ensure their traceability. The general rationale and logic behind such operations should be explained to PolicyCLOUD users, so that this can be considered when analysing outputs during their decision-making process. Users should be advised of the possibility of false positives or false negatives and errors in outputs, so that they are incentivized to critically examine results produced by these Functions.

Several key legal, regulatory, ethical and societal requirements, identified in D3.3 [37], are relevant to the registration of Analytics Ingest Functions, Analytics Functions and Data Sources on the PolicyCLOUD platform, including (e.g.):

- *“Data source quality must be controlled, by ensuring that only reliable sources are used, and to routinely test the analytics components of the platform to ensure that they do not skew knowledge obtained from data in a biased manner.”*
- *“End-users and PolicyCLOUD must ensure that appropriate steps are taken to verify the accuracy of any personal data collected, to maintain those personal data up to date over time, and to allow data subjects to correct, complete or update their own personal data when needed.”*
- *“PolicyCLOUD shall implement technical and organisational measures aimed at guaranteeing the accuracy and quality of personal data included in the cloud-based platform and shall provide means to Data Subjects for contributing to the maintenance of data that is always accurate and up-to-date.”*
- *“Mechanisms facilitating the auditability of AI systems (e.g., traceability of the development process, the sourcing of training data, and the logging of the AI system processes, outcomes, and positive and negative impacts) should be put in place.”*
- *“Any trade-off between requirements, principles or individual rights considered in AI system development should be properly documented.”*
- *“PolicyCLOUD shall only collect personal data, which is adequate, relevant, and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed. As such, for each purpose of processing connected to the Project, it shall identify the minimum amount of personal data needed to fulfil such purpose.”*
- *“End-users and PolicyCLOUD must ensure that appropriate steps are taken to verify the accuracy of any personal data collected, to maintain those personal data up to date over time, and to allow data subjects to correct, complete or update their own personal data when needed.”*
- *“PolicyCLOUD shall keep personal data in a form which permits identification of Data Subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed. Even where personal data are collected in a fair and lawful manner, they cannot be stored for longer than actually needed, unless a reason for further processing exists, and provided that a legal basis for such further processing has been detected by PolicyCLOUD pursuant to the purpose limitation principle. Therefore, PolicyCLOUD shall proceed to the erasure of personal data from the cloud-based platform when it has no reasons for keeping them or, alternatively it shall anonymize and aggregate such data.”*
- *“Should a selected data source be subject to contractual terms which prevent its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorisation from the data source owner.”*
- *“Should a selected data source be eligible for database copyright or sui generis right protection which prevents its use as intended by PolicyCLOUD, that data source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorisation from the rights holder.”*
- *“Should a selected data source, or a relevant part of that data source, which is to be extracted, be eligible for copyright which prevents its use as intended by the PolicyCLOUD user, that data*

source should not be registered on PolicyCLOUD without proper authorisation from the rights holder.”

As detailed in Sections 2.1 and 2.3.1 above, the PolicyCLOUD infrastructure gives an initial answer to these requirements by offering – and, in fact compelling – the registering entity (i.e., the Analytic Owners or Data Owners) to document measures taken to address these requirements through adequate fields that were added in the registration APIs, and by providing a logging service aiming to address applicable security and auditability concerns.

3 Data Fusion with Processing and Initial Analytics

The data ingested into the PolicyCLOUD data store from the various Data Source types is being processed / transformed for the following reasons:

- Cleaning for privacy/security issues or for improved accuracy.
- Filtering – to get only relevant data.
- Maintaining only derived insights (by initial analytic) that might be needed for further analytic – as opposed to storing the entire data.
- Format transformation – saving the ingested data according to a common format which is expected by the Analytic Functions for applying analytics upon later user requests.
- Immediate alerts – this aspect is relevant more to a Streaming type Data Source. Alerts capability will be provided, in which Analytic-Ingest Function can trigger immediate alert upon processing of new streamed data.

Figure 5 provides an example for initial analytics on a Streaming Data Source scenario:

FIGURE 5 - THE STREAMING DATA PATH

In this example, a social network Data Source (Twitter) has been registered, and a Cloud Gateway connector (provided by Task T3.3) with the specified filtering ingests data in streaming fashion. Alternative options were considered for the Streaming Engine (as Spark Streaming), and for Software Prototype 1 we have used a solution based on Kafka sub/pub framework connected to OpenWhisk eventing. Given our positive experiences of applying this architecture to use cases between D4.1 and D.3 publications, we do not plan to modify this architecture. The Data Cleaning & Interoperability Analytic-Ingest Function is invoked whenever new data is ready and applies the specified cleaning and

transformation. Optionally, additional Analytic-Ingest Functions can be applied before the transformed data is written to the PolicyCLOUD data repository for further deeper analytics. Optionally, alerting can be triggered when this is specified for cases when the initial analysis identifies urgent situation.

3.1 Cloud Gateways (Task T3.3)

The Cloud Gateway and API component offers unified gateway capabilities to move streaming and batch data from data owners into PolicyCLOUD, supporting both SQL and NoSQL data stores and public and private data. The Cloud Gateway acts as the only entryway into PolicyCLOUD project allowing multiple functions and microservices to act cohesively and provide a uniform, gratifying experience to each stakeholder. The provided Gateway API allows building scalable and robust APIs, while simplifying the interaction and data collection from various sources and providers. The main goal of this component is to handle a request by invoking multiple microservices, by enabling the acquisition of multimodal data from various sources and providers and finally by aggregating the results. PolicyCLOUD's Cloud Gateway and API component will support scalability, high availability, and shared state without compromising performance. Moreover, it supports client-side load balancing, so that the overall system can apply complex balancing strategies, caching and batching, service discovery and handle multiple protocols and implementing adapters for different technologies. On top of this, several mechanisms and microservices are used in order to check and evaluate the reliability of the data provided, by performing filtering of the obtained datasets before providing them to the PolicyCLOUD's internal services and components. Moreover, this component seeks to describe and map incoming data into project's internal flexible data schemas for both data in-flight and at-rest. Realizing the value of real time data insights, streaming data ingestion is also supported. Following the Gateway Pattern, it exposes a set of microservices to users via a unified API instead of providing an API for each one. More details regarding the design and implementation of the Cloud Gateway and API component are documented and can be found in D3.1 [3] which has been submitted on M08 and in D3.3 planned to be delivered in M20.

Furthermore, authentication mechanisms have been applied on the Gateway level, instead of having to implement authentication mechanisms for each microservice individually. Using federated identity and OpenID connect on OAuth2 protocol, the authentication server can be a separate component or third-party service, but the authentication and authorization process will take place in the Cloud Gateway & API component.

3.1.1 Updates since D4.1

Contrarily to D4.1, in D4.3 extra mention and note is given to the integration of the Cloud Gateway component with the project's authentication mechanism and to the implementation of specific microservices and corresponding endpoints.

Moreover, major changes and enhancements of the Cloud Gateways component were implemented:

1. Two main microservices (Twitter component, GTD component) were utilized for obtaining data from external data sources along with filtering and mapping mechanisms as suggested by schemas of the project.
2. The integration of Cloud Gateways with the Keycloak tool, PolicyCLOUD's federated authentication mechanism, and the first version of Cloud Gateway REST API, following Open API specification were also introduced.

These improvements and implementations were reported in deliverable D3.2 Cloud Infrastructure Incentives Management and Data Governance Software Prototype 1 [41] at section 3. We choose not to replicate the information in this deliverable.

3.2 Enhanced Interoperability & Data Cleaning (Task T4.2)

The Enhanced Interoperability and Data Cleaning component consists of two (2) different sub-components, the Enhanced Interoperability and the Data Cleaning, being responsible for (i) enhancing the data interoperability of all the acquired data based on data-driven design, coupled with linked data and Natural Language Processing (NLP) technologies, and (ii) offering all the appropriate algorithms and techniques for detecting and correcting (or removing) corrupt or inaccurate records from all the collected data, correspondingly. These two sub-components are highly coupled with each other, since all the data that is cleaned by the Data Cleaning are immediately sent into the Enhanced Interoperability sub-component for further preprocessing and utilization, extracting semantic knowledge and high-quality information from all this cleaned data.

3.2.1 Updates since D4.1

Two main updates are in enhanced interoperability and the cleaning mechanisms

3.2.1.1 ENHANCED INTEROPERABILITY

Major changes in the specifications and in the overall workflow and functionalities of the Enhanced Interoperability component have been introduced.

More specifically, the SemAI hybrid mechanism and approach has been introduced and more details concerning the functionalities, workflows and pipelines of its sub mechanisms have been presented.

To this end, more information and details on the functionality, the aim and the internal integrations and technologies/tools of the Ontology and Structuring Mapping sub mechanism and the Linguistic and Semantic Analysis with NLP sub mechanism are analyzed and introduced. In this context, the SemAI hybrid mechanism introduces a multi-layer and hybrid mechanism for achieving high levels of Semantic Interoperability across diverse policy related datasets.

3.2.1.2 CLEANING MECHANISM

In D4.1 we reported of the first version of the Data Cleaning component which had been developed and evaluated. In D4.3 we report of further changes for the internal services of the Data Cleaning mechanism: the logger service was totally removed since its functionalities will be integrated in the overall logging

functionality provided in the DAA layer (see 2.3.1). Also, additional validation rules and cleaning actions have been added, which enhances the generality of the cleaning mechanism.

3.2.2 Data Cleaning

The scope of the Data Cleaning sub-component is to deliver the software implementation that will provide the assurance that all the provided data coming from several heterogeneous data sources will be clean and complete, to the possible extent. Towards this direction, the Data Cleaning sub-component aims to provide all the processes that will detect and correct (or remove) inaccurate or corrupted datasets containing incomplete, incorrect, inaccurate or irrelevant data elements with the purpose of replacing, modifying or deleting these data elements, also known as “dirty” data. In deeper detail, the main goals of this sub-component are to (i) safeguard the level of confidence of the incoming data, (ii) investigate and develop mechanisms in order to ensure that the ingested information is not repeated, (iii) investigate and develop mechanisms that ensure information provision when needed, and (iv) design and develop prediction mechanisms that can be used to extrapolate (or interpolate) data in case of temporary disconnected operation of sources.

In order to achieve all the aforementioned, the Data Cleaning sub-component implements the data cleaning workflow providing all the necessary actions towards the aim of consistent datasets across the PolicyCLOUD platform, as depicted in Figure 6:

FIGURE 6 - DATA CLEANING WORKFLOW

In deeper detail, the data cleaning workflow comprises of three (3) discrete steps, each one of them being provided as an individual service.

- **Data Validation:** Ensures that the rest of the PolicyCLOUD components will operate on clean, correct and useful data. Hence, errors are reported for all the data elements that do not comply with the specified rules. As a result, the Data Validation service performs data validation of the

incoming data with the purpose of identifying errors associated with the conformance to specific set of constraints. In order to successfully complete this process, the Data Validation service exploits the Cerberus library³ for implementing all the necessary data validation functionalities, as well as for constructing the needed validation rules. More details regarding the identified data constraints and rules are described in Section 3.2.1.1. It should be mentioned that as illustrated in Figure 6, the Data Validation service is able to process different kinds of incoming data, referring to (i) streaming data that primarily derives from social media platforms (i.e. Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, and Reddit), and (ii) stored data that comes from Webpages, Blogs, signals and local Data Stores.

- **Data Cleaning:** Corrects or removes all the data elements for which validation errors were raised, considering missing, irregular, unnecessary, and inconsistent data. Thus, the Data Cleaning service performs the necessary corrections or removals of errors identified by the Data Validation Service, and depending on the nature of the error, automated cleaning of the information is performed based on a predefined set of rules. Hence, this service safeguards conformance to mandatory fields and required attributes of the dataset based again on a predefined set of rules or the desired configuration, ensuring the appropriateness and completeness of the incoming data. To successfully perform this process, the Data Cleaning service exploits the libraries of Pandas⁴, Matplotlib⁵, Keras⁶, NumPy⁷, Scikit-learn⁸, and Seaborn [5] for implementing all the necessary data cleaning functionalities, based on the identified constraints and rules. More detail regarding the identified cleaning actions are described in Section 3.2.2.2.
- **Data Verification:** Checks the data elements of a dataset for accuracy and inconsistencies after the steps of data validation and cleaning are performed. Consequently, the Data Verification service ensures that all the corrective actions performed by the Data Cleaning service are executed in compliance to the data models' design in the context of the PolicyCLOUD platform. This service ensures that the data will accurately be corrected or completed and the dataset will eventually be error free, exploiting the libraries of Pandas and Scikit-learn.

3.2.2.1 DATA CONSTRAINTS & RULES

Each acquired dataset of the PolicyCLOUD platform includes diverse entities, relationships and cardinalities that are captured in the corresponding dataset's data schemas. Based on these characteristics, the corresponding data constraints (i.e. validation rules) are defined. The following list

³ <https://docs.python-cerberus.org/en/stable/>

⁴ <https://pandas.pydata.org/>

⁵ <https://matplotlib.org/>

⁶ <https://keras.io>

⁷ <https://numpy.org>

⁸ <https://scikit-learn.org/stable>

includes the data constraints that are mandatory to be fulfilled and the constraints that are optional. It should be noted that all of these constraints are taken into consideration by the Data Validation service in order to implement the various data validity checks with the aim to provide guarantees for the accuracy and the consistency of the incoming data, ensuring the conformance the given set of constraints.

- **Mandatory Constraints** that must be fulfilled for each unique attribute:
 - Specific data type (e.g. Numeric, String)
 - Mandatory field
 - Specific value length (e.g. maximum 20 digits)
- **Optional Constraints** that could be fulfilled for each unique attribute:
 - Specific coding standard
 - Value representation (e.g. text formatting "123-45-67" or "1234567" or "123 45 67")
 - Value uniformity (e.g. all times are provided in UTC, all weight values in KGs, etc.)
 - Value range constraints (minimum and maximum values)
 - Pre-defined values (e.g. values selected from a drop-down list)
 - Regular expression patterns - data that has a certain pattern in the way it is displayed, such as phone numbers)
 - Separation of values (e.g. complete address in free form field without any indication where street ends, and city begins)
 - Cross-field validity (e.g. the sum of the parts of data must equal to a whole)
 - Uniqueness - data that cannot be repeated and require unique values (e.g. social security numbers)
 - Logical Error (e.g. female individual with prostate cancer medications prescribed)

3.2.2.2 CLEANING ACTIONS

For the different data constraints and rules that were described in the previous sub-Section (3.2.1.1), the list of the corresponding possible cleaning (corrective) actions is documented in the current sub-Section. The following list includes the cleaning actions that can be used or combined for the described constraints.

- Deletion of value that does not conform to a constraint by:
 - Dropping a whole entity
 - Dropping a specific attribute
- Replacement of value that does not conform to a constraint through:
 - Transformation of wrong data type value
 - Prediction of erroneous/missing value based on the set constraints and rules
 - Prediction of erroneous/missing value based on similar values in the past
 - Creation of a list of features with high percentage of similarity with the same value

3.2.3 Enhanced Interoperability

Data interoperability is the ability to merge data without losing meaning and is realised as a process of identifying the structural, syntactical, and semantic similarity of data and datasets and turn them into interoperable domain-agnostic ones.

In practice, data is said to be interoperable when it can be easily re-used and processed by different applications, allowing different information systems to work together and share data and knowledge. Hence, Semantic Interoperability is a key enabler for the policy makers as it enhances the exploitation of Big Data and improves data understanding.

This is done by extracting and taking into account parameters and information that were not initially apparent, thus creating efficient and effective policies in terms of good governance. The latter demonstrates the need for the modern stakeholders to implement techniques, mechanisms, and applications that focus their operations on the concept of data interoperability and more specific on Semantic Interoperability [6], for increasing their performance and enhancing their entire policy making approach.

Mapping and creating interoperable data depends on a method for providing semantic and syntactic interoperability across diverse systems, data sources and datasets. To this end, PolicyCLOUD's Interoperability Component aims to enhance interoperability into PolicyCLOUD project based on data-driven design by the utilization of linked data technologies, such as JSON-LD⁹, and standards-based ontologies and vocabularies, coupled with the use of powerful Natural Language Processing (NLP) tasks, in order to improve both semantic and syntactic interoperability of data and datasets.

Through these coupled technologies and methods, the Interoperability Component seeks to provide a state-of-the-art approach to achieve interoperability in data-driven policy making domain. Semantic AI entitles this proposed hybrid approach and is a combination of commonly used semantic techniques coupled with the utilization of NLP tasks and methods. Likewise, the provided Interoperability Component seeks to extract semantic knowledge and good quality information from the cleaned data that will be the input to its system, as depicted in Figure 7. This knowledge, shaped in a machine-readable way, will be used in next Tasks for Big Data analytics, Opinion Mining, Sentiment Analysis etc. One of the preliminary steps of this component is to identify relevant, publicly available, and widely used classifications and vocabularies, such as the Core Person Vocabulary provided by DCAT Application Profile for Data Portals in Europe (DCAT-AP), that can be re-used to codify and populate the content of dimensions, attributes, and measures in the given datasets [7]. Hence, this component aims to adopt standard vocabularies and classifications early on, starting at the design phase of any new data collection, processing, or dissemination system. Using for example NLP techniques and tools like Text Classification,

⁹ JSON-LD is a **lightweight Linked Data format** <http://json-ld.org>

Named Entity Recognition (NER), Part-of-Speech Tagging (POS tagging) and even Machine Translation we can identify and classify same entities, their metadata and relationships from different datasets and sources and finally create cross-domain vocabularies in order to identify every new incoming entity [8]. Thus, by implementing a “JSON-LD context” to add semantic annotations to interoperability component’s output [9], the system will be able to automatically integrate data from different sources by replacing the context-dependent keys in the JSON output with URIs pointing to semantic vocabularies, that will be used to represent and link the data as authors in [10] have introduced. A standard such as this expresses information by connecting data piece by piece and link by link, allows for any resource (authors, books, publishers, places, reports, municipalities, articles, search queries) to be identified, disambiguated and meaningfully interlinked.

3.2.3.1 LINKED DATA AND SEMANTIC WEB TECHNOLOGIES

Linked Data are designed to support heterogeneous description models, which is necessary to handle divergent and heterogeneous data and datasets. The Web of Linked Data is characterized by linking structured data from different sources using equivalence statements. To this end, Linked Data provide a perspective for a different kind of interoperability, based on Web architecture principles. Linked Data interoperability is designed to support heterogeneous description models, which is necessary to handle the very different data from heterogeneous sources. A solution to this gives four key requirements for data to be considered as linked data as presented and suggested in [11]:

- Use URIs to identify all types of data items, for example, considering a dataset of technical reports, a unique URI will be used for each report.
- Make the URIs accessible globally by using HTTP URIs. Though this, users can look up the identifiers. The latter will help users of the PolicyCLOUD project to search policies and information needed through the core search engine and catalog of the PolicyCLOUD project, the Data Marketplace, where based on the metadata and semantics attached to the datasets and the policies, the Marketplace APIs will enable the search and retrieval of appropriate information.
- If someone accessed one of the above mentioned URIs, provide useful structured information in RDF.
- Provide links among different data items by including RDF links that point to other URIs. To this end, the discovery of related information will be enhanced.

The World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) has proposed a number of standards to help in the creation of linked data, in particular, the Resource Description Framework (RDF), which provides the standard for linked data resources on the Web. In addition, a number of models have been proposed for detailing the semantics of data described in RDF, in particular, the RDF Schema Model (RDFS) [12], which allows for inductive reasoning on properties and the Web Ontology Language (OWL) [13], which allows for more sophisticated reasoning about data using description logic and providing a sophisticated and enhanced Ontology Mapping. Moreover, a more recent data schema model has also been introduced and recommended since 2014 to promote interoperability among JSON-based web services [9]. Many already deployed platforms or services use JSON as data format. On top of this, the utilization of JSON-LD technology in Enhanced Interoperability component will provide a standard way to add semantic context to the existing JSON data structure, for the purpose of enhancing the interoperability between APIs and

across the whole PolicyCLOUD project and data lifecycle. To this end, the utilization of Linked Data and Semantic Web technologies in Enhanced Interoperability component seeks to deliver structured information, which can be used and queried by a flexible and an extensible way to get a better understanding of the provided data and datasets.

3.2.3.2 NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING (NLP)

One of the main goals of Enhanced Interoperability component is to create a new interoperability framework for linked data. In addition, the Enhanced Interoperability component needs to build strong links between datasets. These links rely on the recognition, extraction, and description of entities from the structured and unstructured data, such as objects, concepts, places etc.

For this, the utilization of NLP will integrate with Linked Data in order to enhance the PolicyCLOUD's interoperability component. Our main focus and goal for using NLP is to combine subtasks of this domain with Semantic Web and Linked Data technologies in order to provide a holistic and hybrid approach of achieving interoperability among the PolicyCLOUD project.

To this end, Information Retrieval (IR) and Information Extraction (IE) are core tasks and techniques within the Interoperability Component. NLP through various methods and techniques will enhance the processing and analyzing of raw documents and texts, like Twitter texts, reports etc., hence in the cases that unstructured data need to be processed and analyzed. Semantic Web technologies coupled with NLP tools and techniques, such as NER, IE, POS tagging will enhance the ability of the Interoperability Component to extract entities, semantic relations and annotate raw data, hence, to achieve higher semantics and interoperable data. For example, Text Classification, Information Extraction and Named Entity Recognition tasks will enhance the steps of classification and taxonomy that will be used during the Ontology Mapping phase¹⁰. Moreover, Text Analysis and processing tasks from the domain of NLP can also be utilized under the scope of extracting required data and information through the raw texts in order to be analyzed, transformed and stored. On top of this, the Enhanced Interoperability component seeks to implement and enable easily constructed, flexible and high-performance NLP pipelines. To this end, the utilization of Linked Data technologies, analyzed in section 3.2.3.1 including JSON-LD files, coupled with NLP services will help to define the types of the data that pass through services to deliver structured information that can be used and queried in a flexible and an extensible way and to get a better understanding of the data.

¹⁰ This interlinking and integration between ontologies and NLP are planned to be presented in D4.4, where also the integration between the Interoperability component and the Sentiment Analysis component will be presented.

3.2.3.3 SEMANTIC ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (SEM AI)

SemAI addresses the need for interpretable and meaningful data, and it provides technologies to create this kind of data from the very beginning of a data lifecycle. Most machine learning algorithms work well either with text or with structured data, but those two types of data are rarely combined to serve as a whole. Semantic web is based on machine understandable languages (RDF, OWL, JSON-LD) and related protocols (SPARQL, Linked Data, etc.), while on the other hand NLP tasks and services focuses on understanding natural languages and raw texts.

To this end, the combination of Semantic Web Technologies and NLP tasks will provide to the project a state-of-the-art approach for achieving semantic and syntactic interoperability and will enhance the ability of the project to combine structured and unstructured data in multiple ways. Based on this approach raw and unstructured data derived from Twitter, as in Use Case 1 of the PolicyCLOUD project in the concepts of radicalization, can be correlated and integrated with structured data derived from a divergent source, such as Global Terrorism Database (GTD)¹¹.

In that context, the utilization of Named Entity Recognition (NER), one of the most widely used tasks of NLP, coupled with the utilization of text mining methods based on semantic knowledge graphs and related reasoning capabilities will enhance the interoperability and the final linking of divergent data and datasets.

To this end, this integrated and hybrid approach will ultimately lead to a powerful and more enhanced Interoperability Component for achieving and providing an enhanced interlinking between divergent data and datasets Links and relations between business and data objects of all formats such as XML, relational data, CSV, and also unstructured text can be made available for further analysis.

This allows us to link data even across heterogeneous data sources to provide data objects as training data sets which are composed of information from structured data and text at the same time. Linked data based on W3C Standards can serve as an enterprise-wide data platform and helps to provide training data for machine learning in a more cost-efficient way. Instead of generating data sets per application or use case, high-quality data can be extracted from a knowledge graph or a semantic data lake. Through this standards-based approach, also internal data and external data can be automatically linked and can be used as a rich data set for any machine learning task. Finally, the utilization of SemAI, in other words the combination of NLP and Semantic Web technologies, will provide the capability of dealing with a mixture of structured and unstructured data that is simply not possible using traditional, relational tools.

¹¹ Global Terrorism Database <https://start.umd.edu/gtd/>

FIGURE 7 - DATA PROCESSING LAYER

As shown in Figure 7 after fetching cleaned data from the Data Cleaning Component, the Enhanced Interoperability Component seeks to implement the hybrid approach of SemAI through two core subtasks/phases, the Linguistic & Semantic Analysis with NLP (1st phase) and the Ontology Mapping (2nd phase).

To exploit what the Semantic AI offers, data first needs to be structured and annotated. To this end, in the first phase cleaned data will be analyzed, transformed and annotated with appropriate URI metadata and controlled vocabularies will be identified and designed through the utilization of Semantic Web technologies coupled and enhanced by the utilization of NLP techniques, such as Named Entity Recognition (NER), Part-of-Speech Tagging etc, through the utilization of advanced and multilingual NLP tools such as spaCy¹², nltk¹³ and CoreNLP¹⁴.

The main objective of this subcomponent of SemAI mechanism is the identification and recognition of entities, which will be further used for interconnection and interlinking with widely used knowledge bases. Moreover, classifying named entities found in translated data into pre-defined categories, such as places, organizations, dates etc, will make feasible the identification, design and utilization of proper widely used and controlled vocabularies and standards.

In addition, the sub-task of Named Entities Linking (NEL) allows the annotation of translated data with URIs pointing into corresponding widely used and known knowledge databases, such as Wikidata¹⁵ and DBpedia¹⁶, while an automatic topic identification and dataset classification task will ensure that datasets topic of interest are proper identified.

¹² <https://spacy.io/>

¹³ <https://www.nltk.org/>

¹⁴ <https://stanfordnlp.github.io/CoreNLP/>

¹⁵ https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Main_Page

¹⁶ <https://www.dbpedia.org/>

Proper topic analysis should be facilitated in order to organize and fully understand the large collections of text data and the correlations among them. In the next phase, semantic and syntactic annotated data will be interlinked through the task of Ontology Mapping. Ontologies are key factors for enabling interoperability in the Semantic Web [14] and have an important role in annotating and organizing the vast wealth of experimental, clinical, and real-world data and their day-to-day usage [15].

FIGURE 8 - ONTOLOGY MAPPING STEP

Under this scope, an Ontology and Structuring Mapping service will be utilized in order to interlink not only URI annotated data with proper ontologies, but also to interlink and correlate datasets among them.

Successful annotation, transformation and mapping of data and corresponding ontologies in terms of semantic and syntactic interoperability of data is one of the key elements of SemAI mechanism. To this end, one of the main objectives of the Ontology Mapping subcomponent is to save correlated, annotated and interoperable data in JSON-LD format and as linked ontologies. Hence, the retrieval of semantic facts for the support of the corresponding data schema models will be feasible. Moreover, this subcomponent seeks to map concepts, classes, and semantics defined in different ontologies and datasets and to achieve transformation compatibility through extracted metadata. In addition, a data modelling subtask by standard metadata schemas will be defined in order to specify the metadata elements that should accompany a dataset within a domain. To this end, semantic models for physical entities / devices (i.e. sensors related to different policy sectors) and online platforms (e.g. social media) will be identified.

These models will be based on a set of transversal and domain-specific ontologies and could provide a foundation for high-level Semantic Interoperability and rich semantic annotations across policy sectors, online systems and platforms. As shown in Figure 8 - Ontology Mapping Step there are several levels of structuring before reaching proper ontologies. At the beginning, the annotation and creation of metadata representations through the utilization of JSON-LD technology is a key point. Afterwards, vocabularies and taxonomies expressed by RDFs are created and in the final step they are correlated and interlinked into ontologies with high semantic expressivity through the utilization of the OWL technology.

On top of this, ontologies are central to the SemAI because they allow applications to agree on the terms that they use when communicating and furthermore they enable the correlation of divergent data and datasets from various sources. To this end, the utilization of ontologies under the scope of SemAI hybrid

mechanism facilitates communication by providing precise notions that can be used to compose messages (queries, statements) about the policy making domain. In stakeholders and user level, the ontology helps to understand messages by providing the correct interpretation context.

Thus, ontologies, if shared among stakeholders, may improve system interoperability across Information Systems in different organizations and domains.

Moreover, linked data can work as the foundation of a common export format for data in the final service portal of the project, PolicyCLOUD Marketplace. To this end, the utilization of ontologies under the scope of SemAI facilitates communication by providing precise notions that can be used to compose messages (queries, statements) about the policy making domain. In stakeholders and user level, the ontology helps to understand messages by providing the correct interpretation context. Thus, ontologies, if shared among stakeholders, may improve system interoperability across information systems in different organizations and domains.

The overall approach that will be followed brings together techniques in modeling, computation linguistics, information retrieval and agent communication in order to provide an automated mapping method and a prototype mapping system that support the process of ontology mapping to improve and enhance interoperability during the whole data lifecycle in the PolicyCLOUD project.

The novelty of the proposed Ontology Mapping subcomponent is not solely the use of formal application ontologies as an initial mechanism to achieve meaningful Semantic Interoperability, but moreover the utilization of divergent domain ontologies to support the formal application ontologies mapping process, integrated into an architectural framework.

On top of this, the SemAI hybrid mechanism introduces a multi-layer and hybrid mechanism for Semantic Interoperability across diverse policy related datasets, which will facilitate Semantic Interoperability across related datasets both within a single domain and across different policy making domains. This requirement relates to local-regional public administrations and business domain, but it also goes beyond the national borders.

Moreover, IT systems and applications interoperability, sharing and re-use, and interlinking of information and policies, within and between domains are essential factors for the delivery of high quality, innovative, and seamless policies. Under this framework, SemAI and its required steps and subcomponents were presented to facilitate its adoption at data-driven policy making domain. Achieving high levels of Semantic Interoperability in the data can help organizations and businesses to turn their data into valuable information, add extra value and knowledge to them and finally achieve enhanced policy making through the combination and correlation of several data, datasets, and policies.

4 Analytic on Data at Rest

Applying Analytic Function(s) on data from a registered Data Source is driven by a PolicyCLOUD user action. The Analytic Function will be activated as a serverless OpenWhisk function, directly triggered by the user request. The data access operation will be according to the Data Source type:

- **Streaming, Ingest-now** – At the time of the user request all the data was already ingested to the PolicyCLOUD store. Over time, the data might reside partially in the LeanXcale database and partially in the object storage, but this will be transparent to the Analytic Function (with the seamless component).
- **External** – for external datasets, data processing requests (e.g., SQL aggregation queries) is pushed down to the external datastore provider and the PolicyCLOUD platform only retrieves the result of this pre-processing, thus never having complete access to the data set itself. Figure 9 continues the example for Streaming Data Source scenario for the regular analytic applied on the data that is already ingested (and cleaned, transformed etc.).

FIGURE 9 - SEAMLESS ANALYTICS ON INGESTED DATA

The Analytic Functions of Situational Knowledge Acquisition & Analysis (Task T4.3), Opinion Mining & Sentiment Analysis (Task T4.4) and Social Dynamics & Behavioral Data Analytics (Task T4.5) are built-in Analytic Functions in PolicyCLOUD, Task 4.6 (Optimization & Reusability of Analytical Tools) will apply further optimization by enabling function composition as well as the seamless analytics framework that enables transparent analytic on data in hot and colder data stores of the PolicyCLOUD data repository (LeanXcale data base and object storage), Please refer to new section 4.4 for details.

4.1 Situational Knowledge Acquisition & Analysis (Task T4.3)

The main objective of the Situational Knowledge Acquisition (SKA) component will be to derive high-level descriptions from real-world situations. This will be done by means of Machine Learning (ML) techniques and supported with use case-dependant models used for structuring the data.

As part of maintenance of the current prototype SKA-HeatMap, the main effort for the upcoming months will be focused on making the component as much general as possible. Currently is tightly coupled to the Global Terrorisms Database, but the idea is that the tool to be able to work with different datasets that are stored in the relational database, in order to produce generic results based on standard formats.

This task will continue working and expanding its functionality focused on the exploratory analysis.

4.1.1 Updates since D4.1

The major changes with regard D4.1 attend following aspects:

- **Functionality.** Contrarily to the D4.1, in this deliverable the expected T4.3 functionality derived from use cases is clearer. As outcome of several workshops centered around the use cases, the requirements of the task T4.3 were defined in more detail. As a result of that, the specification in this deliverable can put the focus on one of the main goals of the task, that is the Exploratory Analysis for providing the exploration and analysis of the data to the policy maker.
- **PolicyCLOUD Integration.** The integration of SKA-HeatMap with the PolicyCLOUD's infrastructure has been defined, realized, and tested. This integration encompasses the OpenWhisk, PDT and PolicyCLOUD central data repository.
- **Alignment with other tasks.** The identified functionality reveals analyze the collaborations with additional tasks such as T4.2 for data categorization or T4.5 for predicting analysis.

4.1.2 Y2 functionality extracted from pilots

In the context of PolicyCLOUD this knowledge extraction will be materialized in several ways attending the needs elicited from the use case. It is worth noting that all the functionalities delivered by the SKA component will have as end user the policy maker, thus they will be always described under the policy maker perspective.

In terms of purpose, at the closure of this document, the main activities identified in the context of Task 4.3 are the following:

- **Exploratory analysis,** the policy maker will be able to visualize main features of the datasets of their interest. As an example of that, the first version of the SKA-HeatMap prototype, for the use case 1, "*Participatory policies against radicalization*", allows the policy maker to explore the terrorisms attacks extracted from GTD by means of a heat map showing the incidence of attacks by cities and by groups.

- Future developments in the context of exploratory analysis will be implemented in a second component SKA-EA which will allow the following:
 - For the “Use case 2: Intelligent policies for agri-food industry” (Scenario A - Sales prices datasets), the policy maker will be able to monitor the sale price of wine as specified in different specialized websites.
 - For the “Use Case 3: Urban policy making through analysis of crowdsourced data” (Scenarios A, B, C, D, E, F), the policy maker will be able to analyze the data by category, type, territory and time, which will result in a set of graphical visualizations that will show, for example, # of incidents, # of incidents per year, # of incidents per geographical location, # of incidents per category per location, etc. The first experiments have been done in Python.
 - For the “Use Case 4 Predictive analysis towards unemployment risks identification and policy making” (Scenario A), the policy maker will be able to monitor age groups and parts of the borough that are most affected by unemployment.

If time and effort restrictions allow and the needed datasets exist, this task also will be in charge of providing:

- Dataset categorization: The policy maker will be able to obtain text-based information classified into categories. The structure of the categories, how the knowledge is represented, and the categories themselves will be defined and provided by each particular use case. As an example of that, for the “Use case 2: Intelligent policies for agri-food industry”, the policy maker will be able to visualize categorized information for report generation based on categories provided by the Aragon Gov.
- Predictive Analysis: More specifically for the “Use case 2: Intelligent policies for agri-food industry” (Scenario C), Supervised Predictive Analysis, for predicting the quality of the next wine crop based on the Aragon datasets (Datasets: CAP, SIGPAC and Production data if available).

4.1.3 SKA components

At this stage of the project, for the SKA component, main efforts have been done in terms of:

- elicitation of requirements, see D2.1 [1] for more details.
- integration with the existing analytical pipelines. See following sub-sections for more details.
- developing the Y1 prototype SKA-HeatMap which is now fully integrated in the PolicyCLOUD system.
- elicitation of requirements for Y2.
- use case discussion for applicability and validation of SKA analysis.
- first experiments of SKA-EA.

4.1.3.1 EXPLORATORY ANALYSIS

For the case of the exploratory analysis, the analysis will be performed over datasets at rest. Therefore, the analysis will be conducted through the data at-rest pipeline.

In that case, for the exploratory analysis, the investigation on the data will be performed with data extracted from the PolicyCLOUD data storage. The results will be stored into the PolicyCLOUD storage to be later offered to the PDT since mostly they will be a data summary in the form of (or oriented to) graphical representation.

Along the previous year, an integrated prototype of the SKA-HeatMap has been provided with the following features:

- Goal: Focused on providing exploratory analysis.
- Scenario UC1: Participatory policies against Radicalization - Scenario A (Radicalization Incidents) interested in monitoring the occurrence of radicalization incidents in a given area. HeatMap will assist the monitoring with temporal and spatial aggregations of terrorisms attacks.
- Input: Data in SQL data bases: LXC database (GTD data source).
- Output: Json-format data aggregated over several variables (Period and regions).
- Visualization Technique: Heatmaps showing the magnitude of radicalization incidents in a geographic region.
- Integration Status: The prototype is integrated in the PC system:
 - OpenWhisk integration, the analytic owner can register the SKA-HeatMap (as an analytic-function) by means of the DAA layer.
 - PDT integration, The PM can invoke the analysis and see the results by means of PDT.
 - PolicyCLOUD storage-LXC integration: for reading data and writing results.

Following steps in the context of SKA-HeatMap will be oriented in making the component as much general as possible.

In the context of SKA-EA the first experiments have been done in relation to the “Use Case 3: Urban policy making through analysis of crowdsourced data”. Some Python scripts are being implemented to loading and transforming required fields to allow the exploration of the required KPI’s.

4.1.3.2 DATASET CATEGORIZATION

In case the effort allows to include dataset categorization as part of this task, for this specification, the dataset categorization will be focused on the social media analysis. At this stage in the project is still under discussion most requirements regarding data categorization, for example: what pre-processing steps (data cleaning and interoperability) will be needed for the data to be categorized or if the categorization process itself will store the result into the PolicyCLOUD storage, what will be the streaming pipeline used for its processing and what matter most what will be the collaboration with task 4.2

Finally, and looking inside the Categorization service, following characteristics can summarize the foundations for its development:

- The main objective is the classification of information into defined categories for reporting.
- The categorization will be applied to the text extracted from social networks, more specifically for Twitter.
- Clustering-based techniques will be studied for text classification.

- The categories will be provided by the use cases.
- It can be assigned several categories to the same tweet.

Figure 10 describes a possible workflow data categorization using RSS feeds as input data, in this case those are Spanish RSS feeds, but at the end the official language to be analyzed will be English. Those RSS feeds will be generating data every time and will be sent to Kafka. This part of the pipeline could be externalized to retrieve data from the PolicyCLOUD datastore in batch mode. In the middle we will have a preprocessor and analytic functions developed in Python using spaCy¹⁷ to match the keywords defined by the user (by an ontology, a taxonomy, a set of words for each category, or others) and get potential useful entities or categorize the text correctly based on the requirements defined. Other solutions and interesting frameworks will be analyzed to perform all the analytics defined in the scope of the Opinion Mining component. The output will be sent again to Kafka to be used by other components or will be stored directly in the PolicyCLOUD datastore to later be visualized in the dashboard.

FIGURE 10 - EXAMPLE WORKFLOW FOR OPINION MINING COMPONENT USING APACHE NIFI

Nevertheless, as it has been commented before, this functionality should be fully analyzed and aligned with T4.2 which perform some categorizations as well.

¹⁷ <https://spacy.io/>

4.1.3.3 Predictive analysis

Optionally, predictive analysis might be included as part of this task. Forecasting future values from historical data might be crucial for some of the use cases raised in PolicyCLOUD. Thus, some initial steps have been done on this regard, having as result the identification of some scenarios for which forecasting techniques might apply. This would be the case of Use Case 4 “Predictive analysis towards unemployment risks identification and policy making” for which statistical analysis of forecasting unemployment rate for the London Borough of Camden will help in the identification of possible unemployment rate for following years. Due to the nature of the dataset managed in this use case, series counting the number of people claiming JSA (Jobseeker’s Allowance) and UC (Universal Credit) benefits principally for the reason of being unemployed time series forecasting techniques will be fully analysed for this functionality.

On the other hand, any work done on this regard, will be aligned with task T4.5 Social Dynamic, for which predictive analysis falls within its scope as well.

4.2 Opinion Mining & Sentiment Analysis (Task T4.4)

As described in D2.2 [2], the aim of these two components is focused on text analytics for extracting the sentiment of a piece of text, for categorizing any kind of text based on a set of keywords defined by the users, for extracting meaningful information from the text, and more.

4.2.1 Updates since D4.1

One of the main different in terms of specification is that the sentiment analysis planned in D4.1 included a whole own workflow for running the sentiment analysis as a standalone version. Now, after the PolicyCloud integration, the sentiment analysis is one of the steps of a more complete stream-ingest workflow which 1) retrieve tweets filtered by keywords, 2) perform the sentiment analysis and 3) write the results into the PolicyCLOUD data repository. Therefore, the sentiment analysis component has been redesigned to be part of a more complete workflow implemented together other WP4 tasks.

4.2.2 Y2 functionality extracted from pilots

In the context of PolicyCLOUD the opinion mining and sentiment analysis features will be materialize in several ways attending the needs elicited from the use case. Worth noting that all the functionalities delivered by the components of this tasks will have as end user the policy maker, as a result of that they will be described always under the policy maker perspective.

In terms of purpose, at the closure of this document, the main activities identified in the context of Task 4.4 for the next year will be extending the sentiment analysis tool for supporting:

- Sentiment over several words (topics) in the same text.
- Provide enhanced sentiment analysis by means of identifying certain entities/topics (NER) in order to accomplish the task of Multi Labelled/Entity Related Sentiment Analysis.

In addition, this task will study the feasibility of providing the following two functionalities:

- Trend Analysis, for predicting future outcomes based on current data social networks. This feature is closely related with the before commented “predictive analysis” functionality, which aims forecasting future values based on existing data. The case of “Trend Analysis” is a particular case of forecasting with a wide variety of purposes:
 - In statistical literature in terms of prediction, the future long-term movements in the series. Trend Analysis, Andrew Harvey [42]
 - Regarding social networks, the analysis sifting to events discussed on social media websites. [43]

In the case concerned to PolicyCLOUD, trend analysis techniques will be fully analysed with the aim of:

- Understanding the current and future trends of radicalization efforts (keywords detection, new entity recognition, new terms identification) for the “Use Case 1 Participatory policies against radicalization”.
- Discovering hidden patterns and new tendencies using Frequency of words/Topic Modelling/LDA for the “Use case 2: Intelligent policies for agri-food industry”.

Most of the needs analysed at this stage are based on social media data, in particular, RSS feeds and Twitter. But this is not restricted to that, other kind of data from databases, opinions, and more, could be analysed.

4.2.3 Sentiment Analysis component

From the submission of D4.1 an integrated prototype of the sentiment analysis component has been provided with the following characteristics:

- Goal: Focused on Sentiment Analysis.
- Scenario: UC2 (Intelligent policies for agri-food industry) - Scenario B (Opinion Mining Analysis) interested in knowing negative and positive opinions of the different products analyzed on social networks.
- Split in two processes:
 - Sentiment Analysis: apply sentiment analysis over a set of raw tweets (as it has been commented before now is one of the steps of a more complete stream-ingest workflow which 1. retrieves tweets filtered by keywords, 2. performs the sentiment analysis and 3. writes the results into the PolicyCLOUD storage-LXC).
 - Sentiment Aggregation: create some aggregates from the tweets (+ sentiment) output by the previous process and write the results into the PolicyCLOUD storage-LXC.
- Visualization Technique:
 - Gauge, to represent the mean of the sentiment_score for all the tweets in the selected time period.
- Integration Status: The prototype is integrated (can be seen in the E2E scenario 2):

- OpenWhisk/DAA API integration: The analytic owner can register the Sentiment Analysis (as an ingest-function) and the Sentiment Aggregator (as an analytic function) by means of the DAA layer.
- PDT integration: The PM can invoke the analysis and see the results by means of PDT.
- PolicyCLOUD storage-LXC integration: for writing the aggregated results.

As part of the upcoming UPDATES during M20 to M32, below are the most relevant:

- Including a time series visualization to see the accumulated sentiment over a period based on a certain frequency.
- Sentiment will be assigned (Positive, Negative, or Neutral) about a specific(s) topic(s), more than one topic might be subject to be analysed in the same text.
- A collaborative work between T4.2 and T4.4 will be done for providing sentiment analysis over specific entities previously identified under a NER process done in the context of T4.2.

At this moment, two python libraries have been made available to generate the sentiment of a text. Next are listed the two libraries with an example of the outputs they provided:

- **VADER** (Valence Aware Dictionary and sEntiment Reasoner)¹⁸ [4]: this is a lexicon and rule-based tool to perform the sentiment, mainly in social media sources. The output of this library is based on three values for positive, negative and neutral sentiments, and other called “compound” that is the normalized value. “Compound” value is in the range [-1,1] going from the most negative sentiment to the most positive sentiment, respectively.
 - Example: {'neg': 0.026, 'neu': 0.492, 'pos': 0.482, 'compound': 0.9798}
- **TextBlob**¹⁹: it has natural language processing tasks, like spaCy, but in addition performs the sentiment in the text. In this case, the output is defined by the “polarity”, that is a value in the range [-1,1], it means that if the polarity is “-1” the sentiment is very negative, and if it is “1” the sentiment is very positive. TextBlob gives an additional output for subjectivity, this is very useful to estimate if the text is about personal opinions or generic texts.
 - Example: Sentiment(polarity=0.95, subjectivity=0.95)

Despite having both of them available, VADER is the default model for PolicyCLOUD. Although this model only performs sentiment analysis over English texts, it comes with a workaround (based entirely on using a machine-translation web service to automatically translate the text into English) which enables processing non-English text as well.

For non English texts, the translation into English may degrade the accuracy (since obviously the final results also depend on the accuracy of the translation) and therefore should be considered for

¹⁸ <https://github.com/cjhutto/vaderSentiment>

¹⁹ <https://textblob.readthedocs.io/en/dev/quickstart.html>

performance issues. Keeping these limitations in mind and the use cases needs so far, only English text are processed in PolicyCLOUD by the closure of this document.

4.3 Social Dynamics & Behavioral Data Analytics (Task T4.5)

4.3.1 Updates since D4.1

The Social Dynamics component, referred to as Politika, has evolved from the version described in D4.1 as follows:

1. Enrichment of the functionality of Politika through the development of a set of editing and analytics extensions. The implemented extensions consist of:
 - a. A 2D and 3D GUI for editing various attributes of the social network during modelling
 - b. A suite of 2D and 3D visualization environments that allow the modeler to view, in real-time, the behavior of the social network during simulation
 - c. a suite of interactive analysis tools for simulation results that provide charts for sets attributes and their trajectories as chosen by the user.
2. Development and integration of a novel, meta-simulation framework for policy analysis and design with Politika. This online framework allows the policy maker to:
 - a. define a simulation model of the policy problem
 - b. identify feasible alternatives through the provision of simulation models for each one of them
 - c. specify a set of criteria to compare alternatives predict the outcome of each alternative though simulation make a policy recommendation

4.3.2 Introduction

PolicyCLOUD introduces a data-driven policy lifecycle management methodology that addresses the complete policy lifecycle: modelling, analysis, simulation, testing, monitoring, and compliance assessment. The Social Dynamics component focuses on the simulation part of the PolicyCLOUD methodology. It is used to estimate the social effects of various policies via social simulation. The data generated by this component can be used to inform policy design and analysis on the possible social implications of various policies with respect to various models of the populations of interest.

Agent-based models and their associated simulation tools have become quite valuable in the analysis of the interactions between individuals or groups in social dynamics as they can capture feedback between the behavior of heterogeneous agents and their surroundings [27]. In this paradigm, agents act independently according to prescribed rules and adjust their behavior based on their current state, on that of other agents and on the environment. Consequently, emergent patterns and dynamics can be observed arising from local interactions between the agents. Based on these features an agent-based

modeling and simulation environment has to provide effective state representations for individuals and their connections. These are usually implemented using a graph-based model. Furthermore, it has to provide efficient execution schemes for running the simulations given the large number of individuals typically involved in them. The situation becomes more complex in the case of online meta-simulation environments as the execution environment needs to handle, in real-time, variable simulation loads reliably, efficiently and securely, while also providing online capabilities for developing, compiling and reasoning about simulation models.

We describe the second version of the prototype for the Social Dynamics component of the PolicyCLOUD project, referred to as Politika. Politika is an interactive, web-based meta-simulation framework for policy analysis and design. It uses agent-based, social simulation as the primary analysis tool for evaluating policy alternatives. Politika decomposes each policy in a hierarchy of goals, objectives and simulation steps following the methodology and terminology used in policy analysis [22-24]. In addition, it provides a series of analytic tools that investigate the relation of simulation outcomes to policy goals and operationalize the criteria selected by the policymakers to recommend policy decisions. Furthermore, by offering a common modeling and execution environment for simulation-based analytics it provides a standard basis that facilitates inspection and comparison of different models for social dynamics. As a result, Politika seeks to enhance the transparency, efficiency and effectiveness of the policy design process. Furthermore, Politika seeks to increase the computational efficiency of policy analysis. This is achieved through the use of concurrency in the simulator that exploits processor core availability in the server during processing and can scale up through the formation of server clusters according to simulation requirements.

Currently, we are focused on validating the Social Dynamics component through its integration in the use cases of the PolicyCLOUD project. We are especially interested in the design of intelligent policies for increasing commercial success for wine brands with denomination of origin. In this case, the Social Dynamics component is used to guide the design of policies for increasing the average purchase motivation for wines from the Aragon region. To this end, we simulate and evaluate various scenarios that take into consideration parameters such as the price, popularity, quality, advertisement effort and levels of social influence for Aragon wines and their competitors to explore different policies for achieving this goal. We are also investigating ways by which Politika will be integrated in the cloud architecture used in PolicyCLOUD. During policy design, Politika can simulate the social effects of implementing a policy. Therefore, it can provide valuable simulation results data that can be further analyzed by the policy making components of PolicyCLOUD. Currently, we are exploring the integration of Politika as an external tool able to cooperate with the Data Acquisition layer.

4.3.3 Simulation Environment for Social Dynamics

4.3.3.1 ARCHITECTURE

The Social Dynamics simulation component, provides an online environment for Agent-Based Modeling and Simulation (ABMS) [28] seeking to simulate the social effects of various policies applied on a population of autonomous and interconnected agents represented as a graph. Figure 11 depicts the

overall architecture of the meta-simulation environment. As this figure indicates the environment includes a user- and server-side system. The user-side system allows multiple users to concurrently interact with Politika through a Javascript web client interface. Using this interface, they can: specify, edit or delete a simulation, browse the specifications of simulations stored in the system, execute simulations, upload/download data to a simulation, examine raw simulation results, and, compute and visualize simulation analytics. All these operations serve multiple users concurrently except from simulation execution, which, due to possibly high computational load, and possibly limited server resources runs one simulation at a time by default. In this case, all pending user requests for simulation execution are placed in wait mode during which they poll the simulator for availability with a fixed frequency. A user request in wait mode starts executing automatically when polling succeeds in finding an available slot. In terms of implementation, on the server side all user requests are processed by a web server based on the Phoenix web framework [18]. The Phoenix system interacts with three independent components consisting of the Social Dynamics simulator built in Elixir [19] which in turn is built on Erlang [20], the Analytics component that includes the meta-simulator environment also built in Elixir and the Database system that uses the Ecto/Postgres [21] environment.

Throughout this section we examine the design of a hypothetical example policy for controlling radicalization in a population. The example assumes that the radicalization process consists in the progressive adoption of extreme political, social or religious ideals in the population through social influence. In this model, each individual has an initial radicalization status, a real number between -1 (non-radicalized) and +1 (fully radicalized). Each individual connects to a number of other individuals through a number of outgoing, directed connections. Each such connection has a contact strength that indicates whether the individual regards this connection as friendly or not. Contact strength is a real number between -1 (enemy) and +1 (friend). Furthermore, each connection has an influence representing the level of social influence that an individual exerts on the individuals he connects with in

FIGURE 11 - OVERALL ARCHITECTURE OF THE POLITIKA SIMULATION ENVIRONMENT

terms of radicalization. At each simulation cycle, the influence is computed as the product of the radicalization status of the individual and the contact strength of the connection. Therefore, a radicalized individual is expected to make his friends more radicalized while making his enemies less radicalized. At each simulation cycle each individual updates his radicalization status by adding to his current radicalization status the sum of the influences he receives through all his incoming edges. At the end of the simulation, individuals with a radicalization status greater than 0.5 are considered radicals, those with less than 0 are considered conformists (non-radicals) and the rest are considered radical sympathizers. The example compares the social outcomes of applying a policy that restricts the interactions of radicals with the rest of the population with the outcomes of a base case of applying no such policy. Restricting of the interaction of radicals is modelled as a reduction of the contact strength of the connections of the radicals (those with a radicalization status greater than 0) with their friends (those who are connected with a radical with a contact strength greater than 0).

4.3.3.2 MODELLING ENVIRONMENT

Figure 12 describes the contents of the simulation models fed to the Social Dynamics simulator. The modelling input for this component consists of the following data sources:

A list of policy attributes and their initial values

For example, in a radicalization control policy scenario these can include the proportion of radicals, radical sympathizers and conformist (non-radicalized) individuals in the population as in:

radicals: 0.15, sympathizers: 0.20, conformists: 0.65

At the end of each simulation cycle the simulator updates these attributes based on the model for policy dynamics.

FIGURE 12 - I/O SPECIFICATION OF THE SOCIAL DYNAMICS SIMULATOR

In figure 12, bidirectional red arrows indicate data sources which the simulator can read and/or update and unidirectional black arrows indicate user-defined data sources which the simulator can only read.

A set of rules for policy dynamics

These rules specify how the policy attributes change during the simulation. In general, the values of such policy attributes are computed based on aggregation of individual attributes. Furthermore, policy dynamics rules can be used to model exogenous influences on the population such as the addition of individuals through migration or the imposition of quotas and other policy measures.

A list of individual attributes and their initial values

These describe the characteristics of each individual agent in the population. For example, in our radicalization-related policy scenario, these can include the individual's current radicalization status, education and income level. During each simulation cycle the simulator updates these attributes for each individual in the population.

A list of edge attributes and their initial values

These describe the relations between agents in the population. Each such relation is represented as an edge with attributes between two individuals in a graph. Each edge contains a set of attributes that characterize such a relation and may change during simulation. For example, in our radicalization-related policy scenario, these attributes include the strength of each connection and its influence over the radicalization status of the individual at the receiving end of the edge. In general, each individual can be connected to multiple other individuals. Each connection is unidirectional. Therefore, bi-directional links are modelled as a pair of unidirectional links with the same attributes and initial values but opposite directions between two nodes. During each simulation cycle the simulator updates the attributes of all the connections for each individual in the population.

A set of rules for individual dynamics

These describe how attributes for each individual are updated during the simulation. Some of the attributes of each individual are influenced by an aggregated function of the attributes of its incoming edges. For example, the radicalization status of an individual is influenced by the sum of the products of the strength times the influence of all its incoming edges. Furthermore, these rules describe how the connectivity for each individual change during the simulation (e.g., creation/deletion of individual connections). Changing network structure and connectivity with individual dynamics rules allows the user to model how graph topology evolves based on individual decisions at a local level. Finally, individual dynamics rules can add new individuals in the population thus allowing the modelling of local reproduction phenomena.

A set of rules for connection dynamics

These describe how both connections and their attributes change during the simulation. Such dynamics depend on the attributes of the nodes at both ends of the connections and on the policy-relevant attributes.

The size of the population on which the policy will be simulated.

The number of cycles for which the simulator will run.

The sampling period (in simulation cycles)

This defines the period with which the attributes for each individual are sampled. Sampled values for each attribute form a history for changes in the attribute values of all individuals at various cycle intervals. Such a history can be later processed by various analytics or visualization methods.

The specifications of a network generator component

This is used whenever the user wants to simulate policy effects on a population generated from a known network model such as a random graph or various power-law networks. The features of such a model are provided as a set of key-value pairs. For example:

```
max_edges: 5, min_edges: 1, directed?: false, degree_distribution: :homogeneous
```

are instructions to the network generator to create a population where each individual has at least one and at most five outgoing unidirectional edges and where the specific number is randomly selected from a uniform distribution between these extreme values.

Network data in JSON format

These can describe the individual and connection attributes of the members of an actual population dataset that can be uploaded/downloaded to/from the simulator. The modeling language used by the system represents individual, connection or policy attributes as keyword/value strings. For example:

```
radicals: 0.10, sympathizers: 0.18, conformists: 0.72
```

may represent the current proportion of radicals, radical sympathizers and conformists. Strings ending in `:` are keyword names for attributes, while the rest are the parameter values.

4.3.3.3 SOCIAL DYNAMICS SIMULATOR

The simulator provides a wrapper (implemented using the Agent construct in Elixir) over the state of each individual in the process that governs its updating in a concurrent environment. During each simulation cycle it spawns a set of concurrent processes, one for each individual, that run the individual and connection dynamics rules for it and update its state using the wrapper.

All types of dynamics (policy, individual or connection) are specified as lists of IF..DO rules of the form IF <IF-part of rule> DO <DO-part of rule>

that the simulator compiles into Elixir functions. In the case of individual dynamics rules, these functions have, in pseudocode, the general form:

```
function (this, global, cycle) {  
  if <IF-part of rule> then  
    updated_this = <DO-part of rule>  
  return updated_this  
else  
  return this  
}
```

where `this` and `updated_this` refer to the current state of the individual executing this rule and the one resulting from executing the do-part of the rule, respectively. In addition, `global` refers to the current state of the policy and `cycle` is the current simulation cycle number. In order to avoid indeterminate updating of agent states in a concurrent rule execution environment each individual dynamics rule can only update the state of the individual executing the rule. Conceptually, individual dynamics rules utilize:

- attribute values for the individual involved
- macroscopic connection data (e.g., number of incoming/outgoing connections for the individual)
- existence, filtering and/or comparison of certain connection attribute values in incoming connections
results of aggregated function evaluations on attributes of incoming connections (e.g., sum, threshold, mean).

As a result, these rules update the attributes of the individual involved and/or manage outgoing connections (e.g., remove/create/update outgoing connections). In order to model reproduction phenomena in the population the execution of an individual dynamics rule can add new nodes in the population as a side effect. In order to be able to manage these side effects consistently in a concurrent environment, the simulator models the population as a separate concurrent process with its own state that receives messages from individuals to update its state. The population state includes a list of the concurrent processes corresponding to the list of individuals in the population that is updated every time an individual is added/removed from the population.

Connection dynamics rules, are compiled into functions that have the following form:

```
function (this, global, cycle, edge, distal) {  
  if <IF-part of rule> then  
    updated_edge = <DO-part of rule>  
  return updated_edge  
else  
  return edge  
}
```

Compared to the previous case, such functions have two additional arguments/variables: `edge` and `updated_edge` that refer to the state of the specific connection that runs the rule and the one resulting from executing the do-part of the rule, respectively. In addition, `distal` refers to the state of the individual at the receiving end of the connection. In order to avoid indeterminate updating of agent states in a concurrent rule execution environment each connection dynamics rule can only update the state of the connection executing the rule and not the state of the nodes at the receiving end of the edge. Conceptually, connection dynamics rules access attributes of individuals at both ends of the connection along with attributes of the specific connection to update the attributes of that connection.

Finally, policy dynamics rules are compiled similar to the individual dynamics rules as:

```
function (this, cycle, size) {  
  if <IF-part of rule> then  
    updated_this = <DO-part of rule>  
    return updated_this  
  else  
    return this  
}
```

This is the case because policy state is implemented as a unique, special individual with its own attributes that correspond to the policy attributes and with no connections to the rest of the population. Conceptually, policy dynamics rules utilize current values of policy attributes while also computing aggregated population attributes based on attributes of individuals to update policy parameters at the end of each simulation cycle. This is why the function takes a third argument referred to as `size` with a value equal to the size of the current population. In addition, policy dynamics rules can add new individuals in the population. In this case, each new individual is responsible for forming connections with the rest of the population through its individual dynamics rules.

For example:

```
IF  
this.radicalization_status > 0 and edge.contact_strength > 0  
DO  
edge.contact_strength: random(0, 1) * edge.contact_strength
```

represents a connection dynamics rule that randomly decreases the strength of connections a radicalized individual has with other individuals during a radicalization containment scheme. The state of the connection is represented with the `edge` variable, while the state of the individual from which the edge originates with the `this` variable.

The simulator permits the concurrent simulation of the behavior for all individuals based on BEAM, the Erlang runtime system with built-in support for concurrency and distribution of processing tasks in different nodes of a server cluster. The need to create computationally efficient simulations through concurrency requires the design of a global execution scheme at the population level that guarantees proper updating of attributes in all individuals and their connections. In particular, this scheme needs to:

- provide immutable state for each attribute that avoids situations in which attributes accidentally change as a result of various side effects during computation
- ensure that at each point in time only one process updates an attribute, otherwise the outcome of the updating process can be undermined

The first requirement is satisfied through the use of functional programming and in particular Elixir as the development environment. This is the case because in functional programming all variables have immutable state as each variable update results in a new copy of the variable. Therefore, data objects generated at different times remain distinct.

The second requirement requires a careful structuring of all computations involved that can provide correct updating of all parameters but also ensure the autonomous behavior of each individual in the simulation. To this end, each connection dynamics rule updates only the attributes for the connection it is applied on, while attributes for individuals are updated only through the application of individual dynamics rules for each individual. Therefore, in its outgoing connections each individual has read/generate/remove permissions via its individual dynamics rules and read/write permissions via its connection dynamics rules. Each individual has only read permissions on its incoming connections. This scheme allows the simulator to run the individual and connection dynamics rules for each individual concurrently as depicted in Figure 13. As this figure shows during such execution each individual runs first its connection and then its individual dynamics rules sequentially in the order specified by the simulation designer for each rule type. This ensures that connection dynamics rules always use the values of the individual attributes set at the end of the previous simulation cycle thus facilitating monitoring of their dynamics and providing consistency in their behavior. In addition, it ensures that only one rule can update an individual/connection attribute at each time, while also allowing the designer to code for scripted behaviors in individuals that assume a specific execution order of their relevant rules (e.g., when coding the steps in a financial transaction). Finally, policy dynamics rules are executed sequentially in the order specified by the designer at the end of each simulation cycle since they utilize aggregated individual attributes. Such rules can only read attributes of individuals while they can read and update policy attributes. Overall, this scheme ensures the proper updating of individual, connection and policy attributes in a concurrent execution environment, because for each one of them there is a unique way of modifying it at each point in time.

FIGURE 13 – CONCURRENT EXECUTION SCHEME OF THE SOCIAL DYNAMICS SIMULATOR

In figure 13 which depicts concurrent execution scheme of the Social Dynamics Simulator for a number of individuals #1...#N, the red arrows indicate execution order in the sequential execution case. The unidirectional arrows indicate data sources that can only be read by a dynamics subsystem. Finally, bidirectional arrows indicate data sources that can be read and/or updated by such a subsystem.

The simulator takes into consideration the fact that a computing system has a finite set of schedulers that can execute concurrent tasks, as this is related to the number of processor cores available. Therefore, at the start of each cycle the simulator divides the population into chunks based on the list of concurrent processes corresponding to individuals in the population state. Chunks are executed sequentially, while the dynamics for the individuals at each such chunk are executed concurrently. For example, if chunks A and B consist of 100 individuals each, the simulator will execute concurrently all the individuals in chunk A followed by the concurrent execution of all the individuals in chunk B. Chunk size is chosen so as to optimize the size of the execution queue for each scheduler. Furthermore, in order to avoid artifacts resulting from the use of fixed chunks during the simulation that result in a fixed execution order among the individuals in the population (e.g., the dynamics of Individual #1 are computed always before that of Individual #2), the simulator generates randomly a new set of chunks at the start of each simulation cycle.

Compilation of rules into Elixir functions presents a security threat for a web-based simulator since it could allow the execution of malicious code at the server hidden in one of the dynamics rules. In order to increase the possibility of detecting such threats, the simulator performs a static security analysis of the code of the rule that is turned into a function. In particular, the simulator maintains a list of Elixir and Erlang built-in functions that are considered to be safe. These include arithmetic (e.g., +, *) and comparison (e.g. max, min, ==) build-in Elixir functions that are further enriched with many simulator-specific functions we have implemented mainly for:

- computing aggregated functions over individuals and over their incoming edges
- allowing the generation or deletion of edges from an individual that satisfy relevant criteria
- adding/removing individuals in the population that satisfy relevant criteria

If a non-allowed function is detected compilation stops and the particular simulation task is aborted.

Furthermore, we seek to increase the reliability of our web-based simulator by monitoring the use of server resources during simulation. More specifically the simulator examines the available memory for operations at the end of each cycle. If this is below a critical threshold that is specific to the server running the simulation, no new cycle of the simulation runs, the results of the current execution cycle are stored in the database and the user is informed about the number of cycles that the system was able to execute and the breach of the memory threshold. This allows the system to abort simulations that utilize population and connection magnitudes beyond the capabilities of the servers running the system. At its current state, Politika runs on a minimal server with two cores and 6 MB RAM. It is able to reliably execute the simulation model represented by figure 14 (in next sub-section) for a population of up to 30K individuals.

4.3.3.4 EXAMPLE OF A SIMULATION MODEL

Figure 14 provides a screenshot of one of the simulation models in Politika related to the base case of the radicalization example we have been using in this section. In this example, the policy-related dynamics rules compute the proportion of radicals, sympathizers and conformists in the population. The individual dynamics rules update the radicalization status of each individual based on its current value and on the aggregate of the influence it receives from the nodes that seek to interact with him (i.e., its incoming nodes). In addition, they clamp the radicalization status of the individual to the range $[-1, 1]$. The connection dynamics rules compute the influence that an individual has on those he seeks to interact with as the product of his radicalization status times the strength of his contact with the other individual. As figure 14 shows on the top menu, the user is able to examine all parts of the simulation model, execute it, view its results or clone it if he wants to create a new simulation model based on it. He can also adapt the population to his needs interactively through the Manage option. Some of the individual and connection attributes in the model (x , y , z , red, green, blue, alpha and radius) are used for visualizing the current state of the social network during simulation.

The screenshot shows a user interface for a simulation model. At the top left, there is a user profile icon and the name 'baba'. At the top right, there is a 'Log out' link. The main heading is 'Base case for Radicalization'. Below the heading, there are several action buttons: [Edit], [Clone], [Run], [Manage], [Results], [Analysis], and [Delete]. The main content area contains a list of parameters and dynamics for the simulation model.

- **Description:** Explores what may happen to a social group when radicalization is left unchecked
- **Distribution:** Public
- **Contact:** a@a.com
- **Size:** 20
- **Generator:** max_edges: 5, min_edges: 1, directed?: false, degree_distribution: :homogeneous
- **Policy related parameters:** radicals: 0, sympathizers: 0, conformists: 0
- **Individual attributes:** radicalization_status: rand_float(-1, 1), x: rand_int(-200, 200), y: rand_int(-200, 200), z: rand_int(1, 5), red: rand_int(0, 255), green: rand_int(0, 255), blue: rand_int(0, 255), alpha: 0.75, radius: 10, scale: 1
- **Connection attributes:** contact_strength: rand_float(-1, 1), influence: 0, red: rand_int(0, 255), green: rand_int(0, 255), blue: rand_int(0, 255)
- **Policy related dynamics:** IF true DO this.radicals: global_count("this.radicalization_status > 0.5", population)/size; this.sympathizers: global_count("this.radicalization_status > 0 and this.radicalization_status < 0.5", population)/size; this.conformists: global_count("this.radicalization_status <= 0", population)/size
- **Individual dynamics:** IF true DO this.radicalization_status: this.radicalization_status + sum_in(this_state, "edge.influence") ~ IF this.radicalization_status < -1 DO this.radicalization_status: -1 ~ IF this.radicalization_status > 1 DO this.radicalization_status: 1
- **Connection dynamics:** IF true DO edge.influence: this.radicalization_status * edge.contact_strength
- **Executed cycles:** 10
- **Sampling period:** 1

FIGURE 14 - SCREENSHOT OF SIMPLE SIMULATION MODEL IN POLITIKA DEALING WITH RADICALIZATION

4.3.4 Meta-Simulation Environment for Policy Analysis and Design

4.3.4.1 POLICY DESIGN PROCESS AND ITS DECOMPOSITION

We envision policy design as the process that forms policy alternatives and transforms estimates of their outcomes into policy recommendations. The role of social dynamics simulation tools in this case centers on analyzing each alternative to estimate its social outcomes. Assuming the Politika users to be practicing policy designers we seek to follow the actual terminology and methodology used by policy analysts [22-25] and model policy design as a tree hierarchy at the root of which sits a Policy node having a set of alternative Goals as its children. Each Goal contains an abstract description of the desired outcomes of a policy. Under each Goal hangs a set of alternative Objectives for achieving this Goal. An Objective corresponds to a specific methodology for achieving a goal. Each Objective is decomposed into a sequence of Steps, each of which represents a policy execution step in the methodology of the parent Objective. We assume that the execution of each step can be simulated, thus providing a value range for its possible

FIGURE 15 – EXAMPLE POLICY STRUCTURE USED BY THE META-SIMULATION ENVIRONMENT

outcomes. For example, Figure 15 describes the design of a hypothetical policy for controlling radicalization in a population. This specific Policy consists of one Goal (#0) for reducing the influence of radicals over the population. Two Objectives are analyzed with regards to this goal. The first one (#0_0) is the base case of maintaining the status quo. Essentially it models the problem that the policy is seeking to address and provides a base of comparison for the rest of the analysis. The other one (#0_1) seeks to restrict the influence of radicals to the public. Each one of these objectives has a Simulation Step below it. The #0_0_0 Step provides a simulation model of the evolution of the radicalization in the population of interest with no policy applied. The second one (#0_1_0) provides a simulation model of the social dynamics that ensue when a policy seeks to restrict radicals interaction with the rest of the population.

4.3.4.2 DESIGN PARAMETERS

Associated with a policy is a set of design-specific parameters that can be defined at various levels in the tree hierarchy and following a top-down propagation in the hierarchy. These include:

1. *The population model relevant to the policy*

In the case of social dynamics we assume that the population can be described as a graph in which individuals correspond to nodes and their relations as edges. In order to make comparisons and reason about policy alternatives, it is often the case that their analysis should be based on the same population model. Consequently, we assume that the population model should be defined at the Policy level and its definition will be adopted by all the nodes below it. For example, in our radicalization control policy we can define our population model at the Policy level as in § II.B.10. As a result, all the simulation Steps will be constrained to use the same model in their network generator component when creating their population of individuals.

2. *The set of policy-relevant attributes*

We assume that policy-relevant attributes should be defined at the Policy level to determine the relevant policy dynamics that will be simulated and compared in all levels below. For example, at the level of Policy we can define our set of policy-related parameters as in § II.B.1. This forces every simulation model at the Steps level to use the same policy parameters in order for the simulation outcomes to be comparable.

3. *The number of rounds and sizes of populations on which each alternative will be tested*

We assume that both parameters should be defined at the Goal level. For example, specifying the number of rounds at 10 will force each Objective below the particular Goal to schedule the simulations of the dynamics of 10 different populations generated using the population model defined at the Policy level. In this case, a number of 100 for population size will force each Step below the current Goal to generate a population of 100 individuals for each of the 10 different simulation rounds. Both numbers can be set randomly from a range of values supplied by the designer. For example, the designer may want to investigate whether population size affects the simulated policy outcomes and for this he may select a different population size chosen uniformly from a range between 500 to 500 for each of the 10 rounds of simulations in each simulation Step.

Figure 16 describes the top-down propagation of design parameters for the policy depicted in Figure 15. In this case, the blue arrows depict the top-down propagation of the design parameters in the hierarchy. According to figure 16 the values for the population model and policy attributes defined at the Policy level are assigned to the network generation and policy attributes components in the simulation models for both Steps #0_0_0 and #0_1_0, while the values for population size and simulation rounds at Goal #0 are similarly propagated to both Steps #0_0_0 and #0_1_0.

We should note that the designer can override our recommendations and provide values for all the design parameters at any level in the tree hierarchy. For example, he can specify population size at a Step if he wishes. In case of conflict, the node at the current level will use the parameter value closest to it in the path connecting it to the root of the tree. For example, in Figure 15 if the population size is defined in Goal #0 and redefined in Objective #0_1 then Step #0_1_0 will use the size defined in Objective #0_1 as this is closer to it.

4.3.4.3 MODELLING OUTCOME ESTIMATION TO POLICY RECOMMENDATION AS A META-SIMULATION PROCESS

Given a decomposition of the policy design process as a tree hierarchy, the Meta-Simulation environment automatically generates a bottom-up processing pipeline for transforming simulation outcomes of the various alternatives into policy recommendations. Figure 16 provides an example of this pipeline, indicated with the red arrows, for the tree hierarchy described in figure 15.

FIGURE 16 - POLITIKA PROCESSING PIPELINE

In figure 16, blue arrows indicate the top-down propagation of design parameters in the hierarchy and red arrows indicate the bottom-up processing of simulation analytics.

In particular, when the user chooses to execute the policy design process tree then every Step in the leaves of this tree runs the simulation model it has been associated with using the design parameters defined for it. Each Step maintains the results of all the rounds of simulations it has executed along with the population size in each one, both indexed under the round number for each. The results of each Step are then fed to the Objective above it in order to compute at this higher level a set of analytics for each of the policy-relevant attributes defined in the design. For this example, this set includes the average value of the attribute in question along with its minimum and maximum value after all the simulation rounds.

For example (see Figure 16), executing Step #0_1_0 in the radicalization control policy with:

- policy-related parameters of radicals, sympathizers and conformists defined at the Policy node
- population model defined at the Policy node
- population size of 100 and 10 rounds of simulation defined at Goal #0 node

produces a map of results for the policy parameters with keys indicating the specific round on which these results were computed as in

```
{{1: {size: 100,  
  outcome: {conformists:0.24,  
    radicals: 0.16,  
    sympathizers: 0.60}}, ..... }
```

This map is fed to Objective #0_1 which now computes an analytics map with keys equal to the list of policy attributes and values equal to their statistics for the 10 rounds of simulations that were executed as in:

```
{conformists: {avg: 0.34, max: 0.48, min: 0.18},  
radicals: {avg: 0.25, max: 0.3, min: 0.21},  
sympathizers: {avg: 0.27, max: 0.62, min: 0.2}}
```

Analytics maps from each objective are then fed to a set of criteria defined by the policy designer at the Goal above them. Each criterion is defined as a key/value map where key is the name of the criterion and value contains a logical expression involving the policy-related parameters defined for the policy. For example, in Figure 16 we define two criteria in Goal #0. The first criterion named adequacy provides a logical expression that checks whether the average value for the radicals computed in the objectives below it are less than that of their sympathizers, and the one for their sympathizers is less than that of the conformists. The second criterion named effectiveness provides a logical expression that checks whether the average value for the conformists computed in the objectives below it is at least three times greater than the one for the radicals. The meta-simulator automatically evaluates each criterion on the analytics maps provided by its objectives and generates a criteria results map that for each objective describes whether it has passed this criterion or not. For example, in Figure 16 both Objectives #0_0 and #0_1 have failed the effectiveness criterion and only one (#0_1) has passed the adequacy criterion.

After evaluating each objective on the set of criteria defined for the specific Goal, the meta-simulator assigns a criteria-ranking map for the objectives based on the proportion of criteria that each one has satisfied. In our example, this ranking map has the form {0: 0, 1: 0.5} for the two objectives of the specific Goal. The designer can now consult this map to find out which of the two objectives is better for implementing Goal #0.

4.3.5 Future steps

Future steps will focus on integrating Politika to the actual use cases of the PolicyCLOUD project and on developing GUIs that facilitate policy designers with little programming experience to describe graphically the mechanics of their simulation models without having to actually write code in our modeling language. Furthermore, we seek to reflect the political character of policy design by incorporating notions of political negotiation in it. In this case, Politika will consider levels of political support behind each alternative and allow the automatic formation of simulation models that merge and analyze combinations of alternatives to arrive at policy recommendations that could be adopted by a majority and could satisfy a set of negotiated effectiveness-, efficiency- and adequacy-related criteria.

4.3.6 Conclusion

Policy design is typically modelled as following a five steps process [22-25] simply described as:

1. Define a policy problem
2. Identify feasible alternatives.
3. Use a set of criteria to compare alternatives.
4. Predict the outcome of each alternative.
5. Make a recommendation.

Our meta-simulation environment is consistent with this model. In particular, step 1 is implemented by providing a base case simulation model of the social dynamics with no policy intervention and serves to describe the problem under investigation. Step 2 is implemented by representing the goals and methodology of each alternative as a Goal-Objective-Step hierarchy. Step 3 is implemented via the ability to specify criteria at the Goal level. Step 4 is implemented with the execution of the simulation Steps in the design hierarchy. Finally, Step 5 is implemented by evaluating and ranking the criteria specified at the Goal level.

Most of the current ABMS systems [28] offer either an Application Programming Interface over a general-purpose programming language (e.g. NetLogo [29] using a dialect of Logo, Repast HPC [30] using C++) or a special-purpose modelling language (e.g. Gama [31] using Gaml). In Politika we have opted for the second approach and designed a simple rule-based language for agent-based modeling, while providing an efficient execution environment that hides algorithmic and implementation complexity of preparing and executing a simulation from the modeler. The logic behind this decision is to facilitate examination and comparisons between different policy alternatives from users that lack sufficient programming knowledge as is often the case in policy design. Although simple by design, the language is able to express models of endogenous social dynamics arising from local interactions, exogenous dynamics arising from global interventions on the network or combinations of the two.

Agent-based models for social dynamics are receiving a lot of attention because of their ability to simultaneously model interactions at the individual level, at the society level and between these two levels [27]. Criticisms for this paradigm often focus on the ad-hoc character of the models that are developed and on the difficulty of obtaining empirical datasets of populations in which to apply these models [33]. However, these models are mostly driven by processes and mechanisms inspired by a social or behavioral sciences theory, so they have theoretical underpinnings. Furthermore, there are indications that their outcomes are consistent with empirical data [34].

With regards to modeling policy alternatives there is always an ad-hoc character in their creation since policy analysis and design is essentially a political process, and, as such, it reflects political opinions in framing and solving problems [26]. Politika seeks to make this process transparent, efficient and effective by providing a web-based framework for modelling, comparing and ranking different alternatives. Such a framework can facilitate examination of models and comparative analysis of their assumptions, mechanics and outcomes. This will make political influence behind goals and objectives transparent and

enhance the quality of discourse around each policy. To the best of our knowledge there exists no other ABMS meta-simulation environment for policy analysis and design.

FIGURE 17 - SCREENSHOT OF THE POLITIKA GUI FOR MANAGING NETWORK DATA AND VISUALIZING THE EXECUTION OF SIMULATIONS ON THE POPULATION NETWORK

FIGURE 18 - VISUALIZATION EXAMPLE OF SCALED ATTRIBUTE VALUES FOR EACH INDIVIDUAL IN A POPULATION

FIGURE 19 - VISUALIZATION EXAMPLE OF A CONNECTIVITY MATRIX

4.4 Optimization & Reusability of Analytical Tools (Task T4.6)

4.4.1 Updates since D4.1

This section is new as of D4.3

4.4.2 User Story and Motivation

The context of this section is based and partially reproduces the content of Chapter 7 “Seamless Data Analytics Framework” of the WP4 Scientific Report and Prototype Description – Y3 of the H2020 BigDataStack project [16].

Streaming data is one of the typical data within the PolicyCLOUD see 2.1. This may demand high-rate ingestion of data coming from different sources within the LeanXscale operational datastore. Thanks to its ultra-scalable transactional manager and its API to directly ingest data on the storage layer bypassing the SQL query engine while forcing transactional semantics, LXS can handle highly intensive workload, while at the same time ensuring online analytical processing (OLAP).

Here two critical observations have to be done: a) when dealing with high volumes of Data, old or historical data typically becomes cold that is no longer subject to modifications. b) Object stores designed are now considered as the best storage solution because of their cost, simplicity, scalability as compared with traditional databases. These advantages may however be offset by the need of highly performant OLAP analytics on warm data.

The basic idea of the “seamless” component is to present a traditional relational database that ensures transactions, such as LeanXscale, and an Object Store as a single logical data store that will provide real-time data warehouse capabilities. One of the implications of seamless is the need to move under the hood historical data slices from the operational datastore to the object store.

In general, keeping data of a single dataset over two datastores is complex since the data retrieved for a given query from each of the two stores must be merged at the application level. This is a non-trivial task both in term of datastores interoperability as well as of efficiency.

This demands from the application level to be able to perform operations that are not natural to be executed at its layer and which a database can do more efficiently. Moreover, moving data from one datastore to the other introduces significant data consistency concerns, that would typically require operation freeze during the data migrations. This happens due to the race conditions that can occur when concurrent transactions retrieve data from both stores, while a data slice is being moved from the one to the other at the same time.

The Seamless Analytical Framework (SAF) was designed to provide a common interface for the application developer to query data, without having to know neither where the data are actually stored nor the query semantics of the different datastores. The SAF provides a common JDBC implementation

that supports standard SQL statements for the end-user to retrieve information and hides the data stores specificities. Moreover, it ensures data consistency when moving data from the operational datastore to the Object Store, without requiring any freeze. The SAF relies on the transactional management component of LeanXcale to ensure that data records will not be retrieved from both LeanXcale or Object Store even when data is being migrated.

Finally, it supports all standard SQL commands regardless of the complexity introduced by the need to handle the distributed execution of the command. The SAF hides from the end-user all the lower level details about data management and retrieval, thus presenting the operational database part and the object store part of the dataset as a single logical dataset. It provides an interface with which the data analyst or application developer can submit standard SQL statements, whose execution will be done seamlessly.

In addition, as previously mentioned, the SAF periodically and seamlessly moves the historical parts of the dataset from the database to the object storage.

4.4.3 Architecture

FIGURE 20 - SEAMLESS HIGH LEVEL ARCHITECTURE

Figure 20 - Seamless high level architecture gives a high level conceptual view of the seamless architecture. It shows a query execution over a federated dataset residing both in LeanXcale and the Object store. We refer the reader to [16] for additional details. In particular this reference explains how SQL JOINS queries are handled efficiently when they target datasets which are split between the LXS data store and the object store.

4.4.4 Seamless within Policy Cloud

As depicted in Figure 21, we can see that the seamless analytical framework consists of various components. First, the vanilla Object Store, along with the vanilla main building blocks of the LeanXcale operational datastore. For the latter, we distinguish its storage layer with the query engine. For the former, we can notice an additional layer using Apache Spark that facilitates data retrieval by exposing a standard JDBC connectivity mechanism.

The seamless analytical framework makes use of those components, without the need to further extend their codebase. Instead, it consists of three additional building blocks that a) allow the query execution over the federated dataset that is stored in both stores and b) move historical or “cold” data from the operational store to the object store in a seamless manner. For the first purpose, the *Query Federator* has been implemented, which makes use of the core codebase of the *Query Engine* and extends its base functionality that now allows the execution of such queries. For the second purpose, the *Data Mover* has the responsibility to retrieve the data slice of the now cold dataset and migrate it by storing it to the object store. Last but not least, the SAF orchestrator triggers the process of moving data from one store to the other. More details about the sequence of actions that are being executed during this process can be found in [16].

FIGURE 21 - SEAMLESS ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK WITH DATA MOVER

In order to make use of the Seamless Analytical Framework under PolicyCLOUD, a series of tasks need to be performed first. Regarding the Query Federator, its codebase needs to be upgraded to be compatible with the current release version of the LeanXcale datastore. As it has been mentioned, this

component makes use of core libraries of its query engine. At the time when the initial version of the Seamless Analytical Framework was delivered under the scope of the H2020 BigDataStack, the release version of the database was 1.5.5. At the time when this deliverable is submitted, LeanXcale has distributed to PolicyCLOUD its current master release version 1.7.0. The main changes between the two versions is that the latter is now using a more recent version of the Apache Calcite query processing framework, which consists the core of the query engine. This affects the provision of *table functions* that are used internally by the *query federator* to implement the corresponding functionalities.

What is more, the LeanXcale Data Storage engine has been now upgraded to a newer version that comes with the current distribution that has been provided to PolicyCLOUD. As a result, its internal API for accessing the storage has been modified. LeanXcale provides a direct java-based API that encapsulates the specifics for accessing the data storage, as its method signatures are considered stable. However, for components that need to access the storage layer, such as the *data mover*, they need to be upgraded and make use of the current release version of this API. The current 1.7.0 version of LeanXcale is a major update from the previous one, and therefore, some methods have been now deprecated. As *data mover* is accessing the storage using Apache Spark internally, it would require making use of the current version of the corresponding connector. As the connector implements the standard interface of Apache Spark, it ensures that is compatible with the 1.7.0 version of the direct API and not major changes in its codebase are foreseen at this point.

Finally, the *SAF Orchestrator* communicates with the *Data Mover* in order to start the process of migrating data from the relational database to the object store. Internally, it makes use of a scheduler, that periodically sends messages to the *Data Mover* that includes the definition of the data slices to be moved, while also handles failures of the migration process by applying a re-do strategy. The scheduler is configured via the use of static configuration file. This comes with a inherit drawback: if the database administration wants to change this configuration, he or she will need to update the file and restart the specific process. In H2020 BigDataStack, we envisioned that this process should happen dynamically by the use of an extended SQL DDL statement. However, this task was considered as of low priority and was not finally delivered. In PolicyCLOUD, we plan to implement this functionality that will affect the codebase of the *SAF Orchestrator*. However, this can happen in a later phase and it will not affect the migration of the overall Seamless Analytical Framework to PolicyCLOUD for the second phase of the project.

In the scope of H2020 BigDataStack project, the Seamless Analytical Framework was firstly demonstrated with a specific use case in which IoT sensors data was stored in the persistent datastore. IoT data are usually *insert-only*, they contain a timestamp field and after a (use case specific) period has passed can be considered as historical. At this point they are eligible to be migrated to the object store. The implementation at that point supported typical query operations that can be found in data management systems, such as *scans, filters, projections, sorts, limitations* and *aggregations* (with *groupby* support). In PolicyCLOUD we have similar scenarios with data being collected from social media or datasets that consist of a single table and are frequently updated by inserting additional data items related with a newer of time. As a result, the Seamless Analytical Framework can be used to optimize the query processing needed by the analytical tools and exploit the benefits of our component. Our goal is to

validate our approach by using it under scenarios pertaining to different domains and prove that is domain agnostic.

What is more, during the last phase of the H2020 BigDataStack project, we achieved to additionally implement the *JOIN* operation in the *Query Federation* level. This allowed us to use the Seamless Analytical Framework in use cases that use a relational schema. The requirement for the data tables that can be split across the two stores remain the same: they need an increment column (i.e., a timestamp field) and the table should accept insert and select statements. This is a common case however to the majority of the user scenarios, which extends the applicability of our solution in wider domains. In PolicyCLOUD, we will investigate if there is a use case that makes use of relational schemas and can benefit from our solution. If this cannot be feasible, we will continue the validation of our approach using standard industry benchmarks, such as the TPC-CH, which provides a combination of the operational TPC-C and the analytical TPC-H benchmarks, used for Hybrid Transactional and Analytical Processing (HTAP), such as the one we develop.

5 Cloud Platform and Software Tools

In this section we'll give a short description of the cloud platform and software tools that are used for the implementation of the PolicyCLOUD platform, and explanation of their suitability and the reasoning for their selection.

5.1 Updates since D4.1

We do not report of any significant evolution from D4.1 for the Cloud Platform and the Software tools. This proves the soundness of our initial choices.

In each of the subsection we report how our initial architecture choices as reported in D4.1 were indeed good fits for the PolicyCLOUD as of the submission of this deliverable.

5.2 Kubernetes cluster

The first design question for the PolicyCLOUD platform related to the underlying virtualization platform: virtual machines or containers? We chose the container-based solution for the following reasons:

- Efficient application deployment and overall CI/CD cycle
- Excellent suitability for a serverless function-based platform, with the extensibility and reusability requirements of PolicyCLOUD
- Suitability for micro-services architecture, which enable easy deployment and separation of the PolicyCLOUD components
- Portability over cloud providers
- Growing popularity and eco system development, especially in the open-source communities

Once the container direction was decided, the Kubernetes²⁰ container management platform was a clear choice. Kubernetes is the leading open-source container management platform used in production of growing number of enterprises as the base of private on-prem cloud, as well as offered by almost all cloud providers as a managed dedicated cluster. It provides a framework to run distributed systems resiliently by taking care of scaling, load balancing and failover (e.g. if a container goes down, another container automatically restarts) for the containerized applications and provides deployment patterns that drastically simplify application deployment and management.

²⁰ Kubernetes is an open-source container-orchestration system for automating computer <https://kubernetes.io>

As of D4.3 we can report that all software components of PolicyCLOUD have been deployed on a Kubernetes cluster which was chosen as the underlying application management platform. In particular this choice eased the integration of the “seamless” technology (see new section 4.4 in this document).

5.3 OpenWhisk cluster

Apache OpenWhisk²¹ is an open source lightweight serverless platform that provides capability to deploy functions (written in any language) and specify triggers and rules by which the functions are executed. It offers a simple programming model where the function developer can concentrate only on the mere logic of the function, while the deployment and activation details are taken care of transparently. It is based on containers as the functions’ wrapper and deploys and integrates perfectly on a Kubernetes environment. As described in section 2.2.3 , all analytic functions in PolicyCLOUD will be deployed as OpenWhisk functions, with appropriate triggers and activation rules, addressing the extendibility and reusability requirements. Additional important capability of OpenWhisk is the composition of functions to be activated per trigger/rule, which enable to specify multiple analytics to be applied in series to a data source.

As of D4.3 we can report that this choice has proven itself, in particular in view of the two fully integrated use case that were demonstrated during the project interim review in May 2021 where in particular Apache OpenWhisk was instrumental to the implementation of the data demonstrated pipelines.

5.4 LeanXcale database

LeanXcale database is an integral part of the PolicyCLOUD data repository, along with the *object store*. It is a relational datastore, which ensures transactional semantics and provides ACID (Atomicity, Consistency, Isolation, and Durability) properties and offers a JDBC interface, supporting standard SQL queries. Moreover, it provides an internal key-value store that can be used in cases that very low latency is a requirement to support data ingestions at very high rates, achieving a very high throughput.

The database consists of three main pillars: the data storage itself, the scalable transactional manager and the relational query engine. Each of those pillars can be scaled out independently, thus being able to support very high loads. Its support for transactions is based on the recently adopted *snapshot isolation* paradigm that removes the need for data locking often used in traditional implementations, and therefore allows concurrent support for operational (OLTP) and analytical (OLAP) processing on the same dataset. This means that the analytical functions of the PolicyCLOUD can perform analytics on the operational datastore that has all recent updates, and not on a data warehouse that typically holds an

²¹ Apache OpenWhisk is an open source, distributed Serverless platform that executes functions <https://openwhisk.apache.org>

outdated snapshot of the dataset., Analytics take place as data are being ingested into the platform, thus removing the necessity of performing cost-expensive ETLs for migrating data from the operational datastore to a data warehouse that can be used for these purposes. Finally, it provides polyglot capabilities for federated query processing over different datastores and can be used as a common endpoint to retrieve and pre-process data from external data sources in a seamless manner.

Figure depicts the main architectural components of the LeanXscale datastore.

FIGURE 22 - LEANXSCALE DATASTORE ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN

In the architectural design, we can see the three main pillars. At the bottom layer lays the data storage component. Its central component is the KiVi storage engine, which is responsible for persistently store data items to the disk. It allows data items to be stored in a tabular format, providing additionally support for data indexing. Internally, it comes with its own query processing that not only allows for the traditional get/put operations that can be used in traditional key-value stores, but additionally, it exposes a rich interface that supports the majority of the SQL standard operations. The data analyst and application developer can take advantage of it for letting the Storage Engine perform operations like scans, filtering, ordering on columns that are indexed and aggregations, thus letting the engine do the pre-processing, without having to return the whole dataset to the application or the analytics layers. The KiVi storage engine is implemented in C programming language; however, it also provides a JNI Connector that wraps this functionality over a Java-based implementation. Finally, as the whole LeanXscale solution provides polyglot support, allowing the application developer to access data from external data sources, we can assume that those datastore providers are also part of an extended Data Storage layer. For each one of those, a specific wrapper has been implemented in order to allow the transparent access by the upper layers of the solution. The wrappers implement the same interface that can be used by the *query*

processor of the *query engine*. This allows to execute queries that can join datasets that they are either stored internally in the PolicyCLOUD repository, or they are persistently stored in external data stores.

On top of the Data Storage component, there is the Query Engine of LeanXcale. It supports statements writing in standard SQL language and internally it provides a parallel OLAP engine that can be used to efficiently execute analytical queries. The latter allows for inter and intra query and operation processing, thus making it possible for a query statement to be executed in a distributed manner. When a SQL statement is received, then the query engine compiler transforms it to a structural format: the SQL operations are transformed into a tree of operations. Then, the *optimizer* applies various transformation rules that produce different representations of the tree, which returns an equivalent result with the original one. It then calculates the cost of execution of each of those operations and decides about the optimal query execution: the execution that would require the minimum I/O access in the storage level and will make the minimum calculations in the query engine side. When the optimal execution plan has been decided, it is sent to the *processor* that establishes the data pipeline of the operations for data retrieval and starts retrieving data. It is important to mention that due to the intra-operation parallelism of engine, each of the operations can be executed in a distributed manner: for query operations that can be pushed down entirely to the storage engine (i.e. scans, filters, aggregations etc.) they are executed in a distributed manner among the data nodes, while for operations that need to be implemented in the relational query engine (i.e. joins) their execution is also distributed among the nodes of the query engine. This allows the LeanXcale data base to exploit a huge level of parallelism while executing a query, and additionally, execute the load in nodes that are not busy and does not consume many resources at that time. As depicted from Figure , query engine comes with the *polyglot enabler* component which interacts with the *wrappers* of the external data stores, thus, the *query processing* can establish a data pipeline where one of the operators can retrieve data from one external source, in a seamless way.

Moreover, the *transactional manager* is depicted vertically in the overall architecture since it ensures transactional semantics across the stack. It relies on the *snapshot isolation* paradigm, which removes the need for adding and maintaining locks on data items, which is usually the case in traditional relational datastores that rely on the *two-phase locking* protocol. By not having to maintain all these locks introduced by transactions, we removed the inherent bottleneck that those protocols suffer, and as a result, our solution can scale out adequately and can serve operational workloads coming at very high rates. Both the query engine and the storage engine interact with the *transactional manager*, which ensures transactional semantics even if the data is directly ingested in the data storage and the data analytics are served by the query engine.

Regarding data connectivity, there are two ways for accessing the LeanXcale datastore: Either with the direct KiVi API, or with a JDBC implementation. The former exposes a MongoDB-like interface and accesses the storage by bypassing the query engine. This removes the inherent footprint that the query engine natively introduces and can be used in cases when there is the need to support data ingestion at very high rates. It makes possible for the application developer and the data analyst to exploit the unique characteristics of the storage layer; however, it comes with a drawback as its API is not standard. In order to overcome this, we provided specific connectors for a variety of popular frameworks that can be used instead, such for Apache Spark, Kafka, NiFi etc. Moreover, an implementation of the standard JDBC is also

provided that allows access via the query engine of the datastore and its parallel OLAP engine. This allows the integration with popular analytical frameworks that are currently used for ML/DL algorithms that the majority of the analytical functions of PolicyCLOUD exploit. All those frameworks are compatible with JDBC and can push the execution of the query statement down to the datastore level, either by using JDBC connections or by using the LeanXcale connectors. That way, we can avoid the transmission of the whole dataset to those frameworks and instead, perform all pre-processing for data retrieval locally at the nodes where the data is actually stored. In combination with the level of parallelism that the OLAP engine supports, it allows for effective query execution in a standardized manner.

The LeanXcale datastore can be deployed either directly on bare metal or over a container orchestration tool such as docker. The LeanXcale datastore has been containerized, which facilitates the deployment over a Kubernetes cluster. It is important to mention that when using Kubernetes, the whole datastore installation can either be deployed within a single pod or over several pods. Moreover, as previously stated, each of the components can scale out independently. This allows for a great flexibility of deployments, as the database administrator can scale the data storage and query engine nodes for supporting increased data load, or the transactional manager components for supporting increased operational workload with hundreds of thousands of transactions per second. The administrator activities that might be required for fault-tolerance or to scale out the deployment can be facilitated with the automation process provided by Kubernetes.

5.5 Spark cluster

Apache Spark²² is a highly popular open-source analytic engine for large-scale data processing. It achieves high performance for both batch and streaming data and is powered by numerous open-source libraries such as SQL, streaming and machine learning to manipulate and query data. By D4.3 Spark has already been used in PolicyCLOUD in conjunction with the LeanXcale database to provide seamless analytic on hot and cold data at rest (see new section 4.4), where the Spark SQL with optimization exploited from the BigDataStack EU²³ project can be used for queries on the colder data in the object storage.

5.6 Object storage

Object Storage is a storage architecture providing high capacity at low cost, and is a definite choice for big data that is once-written, i.e., is not going to be modified after being written (to modify any part of an object, it needs to be fully deleted and re-written). An object can have metadata (that is used e.g. to increase analytics performance by skipping irrelevant objects), and in contracts to the object itself, its

²² <https://spark.apache.org/>

²³ <https://bigdatastack.eu/content/seamless/>

metadata can be modified. The object storage platform is accessed through RESTful HTTP of PUT/GET/POST/DELETE operations on objects. In contrast to file system, there is a flat namespace. Object storage is offered today by almost all cloud providers e.g. Amazon S3, IBM COS, Google Cloud Storage. Object Storage was a clear choice in PolicyCLOUD for the colder big data store as now demonstrated in the new section 4.4.

6 Conclusion

We provided in this document an important update of the architecture of the Data Acquisition and Analytics Layer and included components. This is a result of requirement analysis and design sessions conducted in the scope of Work Package 4 and in the global project scope for inter-layers aspects. The document introduces new topics such as “Security and Legal concerns” (2.3) and “Optimization & Reusability of Analytical Tools” (4.4) as well as a very much enhanced “Social Dynamics & Behavioral Analytics” (4.3).

The provided architecture details may still be enhanced as the project will progress with actual application of the architecture to additional use cases.

Our next steps comprise the following main improvements:

- Verify and apply our current WP4 architecture against the additional use cases
- Integrate access control (WP3) with WP4 architecture
- Further improve and integrate WP4 features to the framework, including the cloud gateway
- Integrate the Social Dynamics technology with the PolicyCLOUD framework. Further details in 4.3.5
- Integrate and make use of the seamless technology within the PolicyCLOUD framework
- Enhance the data operability component

7 References

- [1] PolicyCLOUD D2.1 - STATE OF THE ART & REQUIREMENTS ANALYSIS. Pavlos Kranas. June 2020
- [2] PolicyCLOUD D2.2 - CONCEPTUAL MODEL & REFERENCE ARCHITECTURE. Panayiotis Michael. 2020
- [3] PolicyCLOUD D3.1 - Cloud Infrastructure Incentives Management and Data Governance Design and Open Specification 1
- [4] Hutto, C.J. & Gilbert, E.E. (2014). VADER: A Parsimonious Rule-based Model for Sentiment Analysis of Social Media Text. Eighth International Conference on Weblogs and Social Media (ICWSM-14). Ann Arbor, MI, June 2014.
- [5] Seaborn: statistical data visualization, <https://seaborn.pydata.org/>.
- [6] Motta, G., Puccinelli, R., Reggiani, L., and Saccone, M., Extracting Value from Grey Literature: processes and technologies for aggregating and analyzing the hidden «big data» treasure of organizations. Grey Journal (TGJ), vol. 12, no. 1, 2016.
- [7] DCAT Application profile for data portals in Europe (DCAT-AP), <https://op.europa.eu/en/web/eu-vocabularies/dcat-ap>.
- [8] Hellmann S., Lehmann J., Auer S., and Brümmer M., Integrating NLP using Linked Data, 12th International Semantic Web Conference, pp. 21-25, 2013.
- [9] JSON-LD - JSON for Linking Data, <http://json-ld.org>.
- [10] Xin J., Afrasiabi C., Lelong S., Adesara J., Tsueng G., Su A. I., and Wu C., Cross-linking BioThings APIs through JSON-LD to facilitate knowledge exploration, BMC bioinformatics, 19(1), 30, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12859-018-2041-5>, 2018.
- [11] T. Berners-Lee, Linked Data - Design Issues, www.w3.org, 2006.
- [12] D. Brickley, and R. V. Guha, Resource Description Framework (RDF) Schema Specification 1.0: W3C, 2000.
- [13] D. L. McGuinness, and F. Van Harmelen, OWL Web Ontology Language Overview. W3C recommendation, World Wide Web Consortium, 2004.
- [14] T. Berners-Lee, The semantic web, Scientific American, Vol. 284(5), pp. 35–43, 2001.
- [15] Groß A., Pruski C., and Rahm E, Evolution of biomedical ontologies and mappings: overview of recent approaches. Computational and structural biotechnology journal, Vol. 14, pp. 333-340, 2016.

- [16] H2020 BigDataStack deliverable D4.3 <https://bigdatastack.eu/deliverables/d43-%E2%80%93-wp4-scientific-report-and-prototype-description-%E2%80%93-y3>
- [17] C. F. Manski, *Public Policy in an Uncertain World: Analysis and Decisions*, Harvard University Press, 2013.
- [18] <https://www.phoenixframework.org/>
- [19] <https://elixir-lang.org/>
- [20] <https://www.erlang.org/>
- [21] <https://github.com/elixir-ecto>
- [22] W. N. Dunn, *Public Policy Analysis: An Introduction*, Routledge, 2017.
- [23] E. Bardach, E. Patashnik. *A Practical Guide for Policy Analysis* (6th ed.), Sage, 2020.
- [24] R. Meltzer, A. Schwartz, *Policy Analysis as Problem Solving*. Routledge, 2019.
- [25] M. Mintrom, *Contemporary Policy Analysis*. Oxford University Press, 2012.
- [26] P. Cairney, *The Politics of Policy Analysis*, Palgrave Macmillan, 2021.
- [27] Will, M., Groeneveld, J., Frank, K. & Müller, B. “Combining social network analysis and agent-based modelling to explore dynamics of human interaction: A review,” *Socio-Environmental Systems Modelling*, vol. 2, 2020.
- [28] S. Abar, G. K. Theodoropoulos, P. Lemarinier, G. M.P. O’Hare, “Agent Based Modelling and Simulation tools: A review of the state-of-art software”, *Computer Science Review*, vol. 24, Elsevier, 2017.
- [29] <https://ccl.northwestern.edu/netlogo/>
- [30] https://repast.github.io/repast_hpc.html
- [31] <https://gama-platform.github.io/>
- [32] <http://epinoetic.org/Politika/politikaDemo.mp4>
- [33] S. O. Bhakti, Y. Levent, F. Klügl, T. Takao, C M. Macal, “Credible Agent-Based Simulation – An Illusion or only a Step away?”, *Proceedings of the 2019 Winter Simulation Conference*, N. Mustafee, K.-H.G. Bae, S.Lazarova-Molnar, M. Rabe, C. Szabo, P. Haas, and Y.-J. Son, eds, 2019.
- [34] F. Taghikhah, T. Filatova, A. Voinov, “Where Does Theory Have It Right? A Comparison of Theory-Driven and Empirical Agent Based Models”, *Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation* 24 (2) 4, 2021.
- [35] <http://epinoetic.org:4000>

- [36] <https://d3js.org/>
- [37] PolicyCLOUD. D3.3 – PolicyCLOUD’s Societal and Ethical Requirements & Guidelines. Audino Alice. 2020
- [38] [HIGH-LEVEL EXPERT GROUP ON AI, *Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI*, <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>](https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai), retrieved 2021-07-22.
- [39] UK INFORMATION COMMISSIONER’S OFFICE, *Trade-offs*, <https://ico.org.uk/about-the-ico/news-and-events/ai-blog-trade-offs/>, retrieved 2021-07-22.
- [40] EUROPEAN UNION AGENCY FOR CYBERSECURITY, *EUCS – Cloud Services Scheme*, <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/eucs-cloud-service-scheme>, retrieved 2021-07-22.
- [41] PolicyCLOUD D3.2 - CLOUD INFRASTRUCTURE INCENTIVES MANAGEMENT AND DATA GOVERNANCE SOFTWARE PROTOTYPE 1, Giannis Ledakis, November 2020
- [42] Harvey, Andrew. "Trend analysis." *Wiley StatsRef: Statistics Reference Online* (2014): 1-21
- [43] Mehmood, Asad, Abdul S. Palli, and M. N. A. Khan. "A study of sentiment and trend analysis techniques for social media content." *International Journal of Modern Education and Computer Science* 6.12 (2014): 47.